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RESEARCH REPORT
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**IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGICAL
SOLUTIONS FOR INTEGRATING RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES INTO RAILWAY
ELECTRICAL NETWORKS**

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SUMMARY

Research Report: 135 pages, 24 figures, 185 references

Keywords: railway power grid; renewable energy sources (RES); RES integration; energy efficiency; transport decarbonization; energy security; solar energy; wind energy; energy storage systems; sustainable development

This study investigates the integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into railway power systems as a means of improving energy efficiency, enhancing environmental sustainability, and reducing dependence on conventional energy resources. The railway power grid considered in this work supplies electricity to rolling stock as well as stationary infrastructure, including stations, signaling systems, lighting, depot facilities, and other railway assets.

The primary objective of the research is to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating renewable energy technologies into railway energy systems. Particular attention is given to optimizing energy consumption, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and improving the overall resilience and sustainability of railway infrastructure.

To achieve this objective, the study addresses several key tasks. First, it analyzes the current state and energy structure of railway power systems, including the relative contribution of conventional and renewable energy sources. Second, it evaluates the technical characteristics, advantages, and limitations of various renewable energy technologies suitable for railway applications. Third, it proposes a conceptual framework for integrating RES into railway power grids, taking into account technical, economic, and environmental constraints. In addition, the study assesses the regional potential for renewable energy deployment based on climatic and geographical conditions, and develops practical recommendations for implementation, including regulatory, financial, and organizational considerations. Finally, the impact of the proposed solutions on system efficiency, environmental performance, and economic viability is evaluated, and future development pathways for railway energy infrastructure are outlined.

The relevance of this research is driven by the rapid growth in global energy demand and the depletion of fossil fuel resources, which necessitate a transition toward sustainable energy systems. Renewable energy technologies—such as solar, wind, geothermal, hydropower, and biomass—offer environmentally friendly alternatives that can significantly reduce the carbon footprint of the energy sector.

Railway transport is widely recognized as one of the most energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable modes of transportation. However, many railway systems, including those in Ukraine, still rely heavily on electricity generated from fossil fuels or on diesel traction. This dependence contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and increases vulnerability to fluctuations in global energy markets.

From an environmental perspective, the transport sector is a major contributor to global emissions, as highlighted in reports by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Although rail transport accounts for a relatively small share compared to road and aviation, it offers substantial potential for further decarbonization. Integrating renewable energy into railway power systems represents an effective strategy for achieving this goal.

Railway infrastructure provides unique opportunities for RES deployment. Solar panels can be installed on station roofs, along railway corridors, and within depot areas, while wind turbines can be deployed in sparsely populated regions along railway lines. Such solutions not only reduce emissions but also contribute to the long-term sustainability of transport systems.

Energy security is another critical factor. Dependence on fossil fuels exposes railway systems to price volatility and geopolitical risks. For countries like Ukraine, which import a significant share of energy resources, enhancing energy independence is of strategic importance. The adoption of renewable energy can mitigate these risks and increase system autonomy. Moreover, decentralized energy generation improves system resilience, enabling continued operation during disruptions in centralized power supply.

From an economic standpoint, the integration of RES offers substantial long-term benefits. Although initial investment costs for renewable technologies can be high, they are offset by reduced operational energy expenses over time. Cost savings can be reinvested in infrastructure modernization, service improvements, and rolling stock upgrades, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of railway transport at both national and international levels.

The transition to renewable energy also stimulates technological innovation. The adoption of advanced solutions—such as energy storage systems, smart energy management, and integrated RES-based networks—supports the digital transformation of railway systems. Hybrid locomotives powered by both conventional and renewable energy sources represent a promising direction already being implemented in several countries.

In addition to technical and economic benefits, the transition to renewable energy has important social implications. Reducing air and noise pollution improves public health and quality of life, particularly in urban areas. Furthermore, the development of renewable energy infrastructure creates new employment opportunities in engineering, construction, and maintenance, contributing to regional economic growth.

International experience demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating renewable energy into railway systems. For example, railway operations in the Netherlands are powered entirely by wind energy, while in India solar technologies are increasingly deployed on trains and station facilities. These examples highlight the practical viability and benefits of such approaches.

Given its significant potential for solar and wind energy, Ukraine is well positioned to adopt similar strategies. The integration of renewable energy into railway systems can support the country's transition toward a sustainable energy future and facilitate alignment with European transport and energy systems.

Finally, the study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and Goal 13 (Climate Action). In the long term, the adoption of renewable energy technologies can position railway transport as a key driver of the transition to a low-carbon economy while maintaining its critical role within the national transport system.

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ABBREVIATION

- AC – alternating Current;
- ADG – Automatic Diesel Generator;
- AIR – Automatic Inclusion of Reserve;
- AMB – active magnetic Bearings;
- AMs – asynchronous Machines;
- APF – active power Filters;
- ARI – automatic repeated inclusion;
- BESS – Battery Energy Storage System;
- CDC – Carbide-derived carbon;
- CEES – Combined Electric Power Systems;
- CRD – Charging And Recharging Devices;
- DB – Distribution Board;
- DeB — Deutsche Bahn;
- DC – direct Current;
- DCV – constant voltage converter;
- DG – Distributed Generation;
- DGA – Diesel Generator Automatic;
- DPSS – Distributed-Type Power Supply System;
- ECS – Electrical Centralization Station;
- EDLC – Electric Double Layer Capacitors;
- EDLC – electrochemical double-layer capacitors (ultracapacitors);
- EE – Electric Energy;
- EMS — Energy Management System;
- EIB — European Investment Bank;
- ENTSO-E — European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
- EPSS – external Power Source;
- ERA — European Union Agency for Railways (European Union Agency for Railways)
- ESS – Electric Storage System;
- EU — European Union
- FESS – Flywheel Energy Storage System;
- ICT — Information and Communication Technologies;
- IGBT — Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor;

IoT — Internet of Things;
JR — Japan Railways;
HV – higher Harmonics;
HV — high Voltage;
LPSL – longitudinal power supply line;
MG – Microgrid;
MV — medium Voltage
MPPT – maximum power point tracking;
MTP – maximum current protection;
NS — Nederlandse Spoorwegen;
NECP — National Energy and Climate Plan
OCS – Overhead Catenary System;
OSS – Onboard Storage Systems;
OT – Own-Needs Power Transformers;
OTL – overhead transmission line;
PEU – Photovoltaic Installation;
PMB – Passive Magnetic Bearings;
PMSM – Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine;
PPA — Power Purchase Agreement
PSFB – Polysulfide Bromine Flow Batteries;
PV – Photovoltaic;
PWM – Pulse-Width Modulation;
RAPP – Reserve Autonomous Power Plant;
RES – Renewable Energy Sources;
RFB – redox flow battery;
SAPF – Shunt Active Power Filter;
SCADA — Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SCB – signalling, centralization and blocking;
SCC – short-circuit current;
SOC – state of charge;
SON – System of Own Needs;
SPP – Solar Power Plants;
STATCOM — Static Synchronous Compensator
TDD – total demand distortion;
THD – total harmonic distortion;
TS – traction Substations;

TSI – thyristor switching Inverter;
TTS – traction transport System;
TWR – two wire-rail;
UHV DC — Ultra-High-Voltage Direct Current;
UZ — Ukrzaliznytsia
UIC — International Union of Railways;
UPS – Uninterruptible Power Supply;
US — United States
VRFB – Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries;
VSC — Voltage Source Converter
VSI – voltage source inverter;
WPP – Wind Power Plants;
WT – Wind Turbines;
ZBFB – zinc bromine flow Batteries.

INTRODUCTIONS

Railway transport stands out as a mode of travel with inherently lower emissions and high energy efficiency compared to road or air, especially when electrified. Electric trains produce no direct exhaust and can be powered by increasingly cleaner sources of electricity, which positions rail as a key player in sustainable mobility initiatives. However, realizing these environmental advantages on a large scale requires not only extensive electrification infrastructure (electrified tracks, overhead catenary systems, substations, etc.) but also ensuring that the electricity feeding the railway is generated with minimal carbon footprint. In recent decades, railways worldwide have pursued improvements in energy efficiency and environmental performance – exemplified by the growth of high-speed rail, adoption of advanced regenerative braking systems, and the use of modern, energy-efficient rolling stock. These efforts reflect a broader recognition of the need to conserve energy resources and reduce transport-related impacts on the climate. In this context, new means of electricity production based on renewable energy sources (RES) have emerged as a promising solution to further decarbonize railway operations. Integrating renewables into the railway power network can enable trains to run on clean energy, significantly cutting greenhouse gas emissions while also potentially lowering energy costs and improving energy security. Studies of fully renewable energy scenarios underline that deep decarbonization of transport will require such shifts – with rail networks powered largely by renewable electricity playing an essential role in a 100% renewable future [1].

The momentum of the global energy transition provides a strong foundation for extending renewable generation into railway systems. In Europe, for example, renewable energy deployment has accelerated to the point that it is reshaping the electricity landscape. In 2020, a milestone was reached when renewable sources (wind, solar, hydro, biomass) for the first time generated more electricity in Europe than fossil-fueled power plants – 38% of total EU electricity came from renewables versus 37% from coal and gas. This “historic event” reflects a steady upward trend over the past decade, spurred by supportive policies and technological advances. Indeed, the European Union’s member states collectively achieved their target of 20% of gross final energy consumption from renewables by 2020, a goal set over a decade prior [2]. Such progress is not limited to Europe: globally, the share of electricity produced from renewables has been rising continuously. By 2021, roughly 28% of the world’s electricity was being generated from renewable sources – up from about 20% in 2011 – indicating a significant worldwide shift toward cleaner power [3]. This broad context of increasing renewable availability opens the door for new applications, one of the

most promising of which is the integration of RES into railway energy supply networks. In essence, as the electric grid becomes greener, so too can electric railways, but beyond simply drawing from a cleaner grid, rail operators are also exploring direct use of on-site renewable generation and other innovative models to maximize the use of clean energy in rail transportation.

Pioneering efforts around the world have already demonstrated the viability and benefits of powering rail infrastructure with renewable energy. In Europe, several national railway companies have taken the lead in committing to 100% renewable electricity and are making rapid progress towards that goal. Germany's Deutsche Bahn (DB), for instance, obtained approximately 60% of its traction power from renewable sources as of 2019 [4]. DB has steadily increased the renewable share in its electricity mix through measures such as long-term power purchase agreements for wind and hydro power, and it has charted a course to complete carbon-neutrality in the coming decades (with plans to reach 100% green electricity well before 2050). Another notable example is the Netherlands: by January 2017, all electric trains on the Dutch national railway were being run on 100% wind energy, a feat accomplished a year ahead of schedule [5]. The Dutch railway operator (NS) met this goal by partnering with wind farm projects – making the Netherlands the first country in the world to power its entire electrified rail network exclusively with renewable energy. These cases illustrate how, in the European context of already extensive rail electrification, the strategy has largely been to regenerate the supply side: i.e. to procure or produce renewable electricity at a scale sufficient to cover the railways' sizable power demand. The successes of NS and DB have been facilitated by Europe's liberalized electricity markets and the availability of certification regimes that allow the tracking and guarantee of renewable origin for the power used by trains. Moreover, they align with broader European Union climate objectives, showing how early-adopter rail companies can leverage the continent's fast-growing renewable energy capacity to decarbonize transport.

In the Asian context, where rail networks are often expanding and electrifying at a very rapid pace, we see a parallel drive to integrate renewables, albeit using strategies suited to different circumstances. India provides a striking example: Indian Railways, one of the largest railway systems in the world, has set a target to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2030. This ambitious goal is being pursued through a multi-pronged approach: complete electrification of its vast rail routes, dramatic improvements in energy efficiency, and the deployment of significant renewable energy generation dedicated to railway needs [6]. Over the last few years, India has electrified its rail lines at unprecedented speed – the electrified share of its route network rose from about 45% in 2015 to 80% by 2022, and the goal of electrifying

100% of broad-gauge routes by the end of 2023 is on track to be realized [7]. This electrification drive means that the majority of Indian trains will soon be running on electricity instead of diesel, creating the opportunity to supply that electricity from renewables. To that end, Indian Railways is installing large-scale solar photovoltaic (PV) capacity on railway-owned land and rooftops, and investing in wind farms, to directly power railway operations. As of early 2023, the railway had commissioned roughly 250 MW of solar PV and wind installations, and agreements were in place for an additional 2 GW of renewable capacity. Overall, Indian Railways estimates it will require about 30,000 MW of renewable energy capacity by 2030 to meet its traction power needs and fully eliminate fossil-based electricity use [6]. Initiatives already underway include solar plants along the railway tracks and at station facilities, as well as pilot projects for “round-the-clock” renewable energy supply through storage-backed contracts. India’s approach exemplifies how a railway in a developing economy – facing growing transport demand and still reliant on coal-heavy grid power – is leapfrogging directly to clean energy by building its own renewable assets and deeply integrating them with network expansion plans.

China, which operates the world’s most extensive electrified railway system (including the largest high-speed rail network), is similarly moving to green its railway electricity supply, though via a somewhat different route. China’s national grid is undergoing a massive transition with aggressive targets for wind and solar deployment, and the railway sector stands to benefit from this overall grid decarbonization. In parallel, Chinese researchers and railway authorities are exploring dedicated renewable integration solutions tailored to rail. For example, studies have assessed the vast potential for solar power generation on railway property in China – including installing PV panels on station roofs, alongside tracks, and even on the surface of protective sound barriers – with estimates that such applications could provide a significant fraction of the energy needed for train operations. Pilot projects have already been launched: in late 2021, a 6 MW solar PV array on the rooftop of the Beijing South (Xiong’an) high-speed railway station was connected to the traction power system, supplying clean electricity directly to trains at the station. And in mid-2023, China’s first photovoltaic-powered railway section began operation on a freight line, with a dedicated solar farm feeding traction substations. These early demonstrations in China highlight both the opportunities and challenges of on-site generation for railways: the country’s vast, sunny territories (especially in the northwest) offer tremendous solar potential, and busy rail corridors present high electricity demand that coincides well with daylight hours, but ensuring the reliable integration of this intermittent generation into a system with very high safety and power quality requirements demands advanced

control technologies and careful planning. As China continues to expand its railway network and as its national renewable energy capacity soars (targeting over 1,200 GW of wind and solar by 2030), the coupling of renewables with rail is expected to deepen, contributing to China's vision of a low-carbon transport system.

Other regions also provide instructive examples of renewable-powered rail infrastructure. In Africa, a landmark project is the Addis Ababa–Djibouti electrified railway, which began operations in 2016. This 753 km line – the first modern electrified cross-border railway in East Africa – is powered entirely by renewable energy, drawing on Ethiopia's abundant hydroelectric resources [8]. Tapping into emission-free hydropower, the railway has been heralded as a model for sustainable transport in the region, dramatically cutting travel time and costs while avoiding the pollution that a diesel-powered equivalent would generate. The successful operation of the Ethiopia-Djibouti line demonstrates that, given the right energy infrastructure, even large-scale rail projects can run on 100% renewable electricity from day one. In North America, where railway electrification is not yet widespread, efforts are focusing on new projects and specific corridors to ensure that clean energy is part of future rail development. In the United States, the planned California High-Speed Rail system has committed to source 100% of its operating electricity from renewable energy. Project plans include the construction of utility-scale solar farms on railway-owned land in the Central Valley, accompanied by battery energy storage, to supply the high-speed trains with solar power fed directly into the traction grid [9]. This approach effectively turns the railway into a self-generating energy microgrid, reducing reliance on the broader power grid and guaranteeing that train operations will be zero-emission. Meanwhile, Amtrak (the U.S. intercity passenger rail operator) has announced goals to achieve 100% carbon-free electricity by 2030 for its electrically powered routes, such as the busy Northeast Corridor, as part of a broader commitment to net-zero emissions by 2045 [10]. Amtrak is pursuing this through purchasing renewable energy (and carbon-free nuclear energy) for its traction power supply and investing in energy efficiency upgrades. For the many rail lines in the U.S. (and other countries) that remain non-electrified, alternative solutions are being tested to integrate renewables into rail transport. These include battery-electric and hydrogen fuel cell trains, which use energy stored from external renewable sources. For instance, hydrogen trains, powered by fuel cells that consume hydrogen produced via renewable-powered electrolysis (so-called "green hydrogen"), have begun regular service in parts of Europe and are being trialed in North America as well. Battery-electric locomotives that charge from renewable-rich grids or on-site solar are also in development for freight operations. While these technologies lie outside the traditional electrified infrastructure, they

complement the overall trend by enabling rail decarbonization even on routes where building overhead wires is not feasible; essentially, they allow the use of renewable energy in a portable form (battery or hydrogen) to displace diesel. The variety of approaches across continents – from direct grid integration of renewables in Europe, to self-generation in India and California, to new rolling stock technologies – underscores that integrating RES into rail networks is a global pursuit, adapted to local conditions and requirements.

The technical pathways for integrating renewable energy sources into railway power supply systems are diverse, and multiple approaches can coexist to form a robust “green railway” energy ecosystem. Broadly, integration strategies can be categorized into two groups: indirect integration, where renewables feed into the external public grid and the railway simply contracts or draws certified green power, and direct integration, where renewable generation is physically embedded within the railway’s own infrastructure. The indirect method has been widely used by rail operators in countries with liberalized electricity markets: for example, railway companies sign power purchase agreements (PPAs) or buy guarantees of origin to ensure that an equivalent amount of their consumed electricity is generated by renewable sources fed into the grid. This approach leverages the scale of national grids and the ongoing greening of the overall electricity mix, as seen with DB and NS procuring vast amounts of wind, solar, and hydro energy through utilities or energy markets. Direct integration, on the other hand, involves connecting renewable energy installations to the railway’s power network at various points. There are many imaginative implementations of this concept. According to Sychenko’s analysis [11], potential avenues include using RES to power remote or weakly supplied railway sites (for instance, solar panels powering signaling equipment in off-grid areas, with backup connections to the traction supply if needed), creating “transport and energy corridors” where railway lines run parallel to highways or transmission lines and shared renewable generation (such as large wind farms along the corridor) can supply both transport and general electricity demand, and situating generation assets like solar or wind within railway premises. One practical configuration is the direct feeding of traction power: for example, connecting a solar farm or wind turbines to the high-voltage side of a traction substation transformer. In this setup, renewable power can flow straight into the railway’s 25 kV AC or 3 kV DC traction circuit (depending on the system) alongside grid power. Another concept is the use of RES at “booster” locations – intermediate points in the catenary system that help regulate voltage on long stretches – by installing, say, a containerized solar + battery unit at a mid-point to support the catenary voltage during peak loads. Yet another model is the development of autonomous renewable power systems for railway facilities: for

instance, a group of stations or maintenance depots equipped with their own solar panels and wind turbines, combined with energy storage, forming a microgrid that can operate connected to or islanded from the main traction network. All these forms of direct integration require careful coordination to maintain power quality. Key considerations include handling the variable and somewhat unpredictable output of renewables, ensuring protection systems function with additional generation sources in the circuit, and maintaining the very high reliability and power quality standards that rail operations demand (voltage tolerances, minimal disruptions, etc.). Nonetheless, pilot projects in Europe and Asia have shown the feasibility of direct integration: for example, the UK's "Riding Sunbeams" pilot connected a community solar farm to an electrified railway line's DC feeder station, successfully powering trains with solar energy without going through the national grid. This diversity of integration methods allows each railway system to craft an optimal mix suitable for its specific conditions – whether that means mostly buying green electricity from the grid, or producing its own renewable power on-site, or (as will likely be common) a hybrid of both approaches.

One critical component that enhances the integration of renewables into railway power networks is the deployment of energy storage systems (ESS) alongside generation and consumption points. The inherently variable nature of solar and wind power – fluctuating with sunlight intensity or wind speed – can introduce challenges for the stability of a railway electrical system that was traditionally designed for steady, controllable input from the grid. By incorporating modern energy storage technologies, railways can buffer these fluctuations and align renewable generation with train power demand more effectively. A major opportunity in this regard comes from the nature of train operations themselves: electric trains regularly generate brief surges of power during braking (regenerative braking), which can be captured and stored instead of being wasted as heat. By installing large batteries or supercapacitors at traction substations or alongside the tracks, this regenerative braking energy can be stored and then reused when the same train (or others on the line) accelerates later, significantly improving overall energy efficiency. For example, Japan and several European countries have implemented wayside energy storage units at metro and suburban railway substations to capture braking energy; this has reduced net electricity consumption and also stabilized voltage during train accelerations. When such storage is combined with on-site renewables, it creates a synergistic effect: the storage can smooth out the short-term variability of solar/wind output, and also ensure that surplus renewable energy (for instance, solar power generated during off-peak train times midday) is not wasted but saved for the evening peak when trains require more traction

power. Mitrofanov et al. have reviewed stationary hybrid energy systems for railway electrification and found that sufficient energy storage is a key element for maintaining power quality and reliability in systems with high renewable penetration [12]. They note that introducing RES without adequate storage or reserve can lead to greater fluctuations in the traction power supply, which must be managed to avoid issues with voltage dips or frequency deviations. Conversely, a well-sized ESS can mitigate these issues by quickly absorbing or delivering power, thus maintaining a stable balance. In addition to batteries, other forms of storage like flywheels and kinetic energy storage have also been considered for rail applications (for example, flywheels to capture braking energy on light rail systems). The development of efficient ESS technologies and their declining costs make it increasingly practical for railways to deploy such systems at scale. A notable real-world implementation is in Poland: in 2021, the Polish rail energy company PKP Energetyka launched Europe's largest traction battery storage facility, a 5 MW/1.2 MWh lithium-ion unit at a traction substation in Garbce, which is used to stabilize the local 3 kV DC network, store regenerative braking energy, and provide backup power [13]. This installation has reportedly enabled a significant increase in the utilization of renewable energy within that segment of the rail network (by buffering solar generation feeding the same substation) and improved the reliability of power supply to trains. Thus, energy storage not only helps railways use more RES by solving the intermittency problem, but it also enhances the energy efficiency of the system by recycling energy that would otherwise be lost.

Integrating high shares of renewables and new storage capabilities is driving a need to modernize the control and power electronics of railway traction power systems. Traditional railway power supply architectures were relatively simple: a unidirectional flow of power from the public grid, through transformers and rectifiers at substations, to the trains, with control primarily focused on maintaining constant voltage and protecting against faults. The new paradigm, however, is closer to a smart grid – a bidirectional, actively managed network where power may flow from distributed generators (renewable or storage) into the traction system or even back to the public grid during certain periods (for instance, when excess regenerative energy is not needed by any train and could be sold to the utility). To handle this complexity, railways are turning to advanced power electronic converters and intelligent control systems. Modern converter-based traction substations are being developed that can flexibly import and export power. In AC electrification systems (like 25 kV AC railways), these often take the form of voltage source converter (VSC) substations that can modulate power quality and even feed energy from renewables or storage into the catenary with precise control. In DC systems, reversible substations equipped with IGBT-based

inverters now allow surplus DC power (e.g., from braking or local solar generation) to be inverted and sent into the AC grid, whereas older diode-based substations could not. As Steimel discussed, power-electronic supply interfaces for railway grids are a cornerstone of future traction power systems, enabling not only the accommodation of renewable inputs but also improving the overall efficiency and stability of the system [14]. These interfaces can dynamically regulate voltage, filter out harmonics, and manage the load flow between different feeders – functions that become critical when intermittent sources are in the mix. Alongside hardware upgrades, sophisticated control algorithms and communication infrastructure (the realm of ICT – information and communication technologies) are being implemented to supervise and optimize the railway energy network in real time. This includes demand forecasting (predicting the electrical load of trains based on timetables and operational conditions), generation forecasting (especially for solar and wind inputs), and intelligent dispatch of storage. Recent developments in smart grid ICT, as noted by Rehmani et al., emphasize distributed control and IoT-based monitoring for integrating renewables into power networks [15]. In a railway context, this means equipping substations and sectioning posts with sensors and control units that can react to changes – for example, temporarily reducing a train’s acceleration power draw if a cloud transient causes solar generation to drop, or conversely, boosting supply from a battery when multiple trains accelerate simultaneously. The concept of an “intelligent traction power system” is emerging: one that can automatically balance input from the main grid, on-site renewables, energy storage, and the variable consumption of moving trains, all while maintaining the rigorous safety and reliability standards of railway operations.

A real-world illustration of these innovations is again provided by Poland’s PKP Energetyka, which has been developing a comprehensive program called “Green Railway” to integrate RES and smart grid tech into the Polish railway network. In addition to installing large-scale batteries, the company has deployed an advanced grid management platform that uses machine learning to forecast both the traction load and the production from solar farms connected to the railway energy system [13]. By analyzing data (including weather forecasts, train schedules, and real-time measurements), the system can predict when there might be surplus solar energy that could charge an energy storage or when a peak in train demand is approaching that might require extra support from storage or the public grid. This kind of digital integration exemplifies the cutting-edge of railway energy management – effectively creating a mini smart grid dedicated to rail, which mirrors the transformations happening in the wider electric power industry. The result is a more resilient and efficient system, capable of maximizing the use of intermittent renewable sources

without compromising the continuity of train operations. Notably, the “Green Railway” program aims to source 85% of the Polish railway’s electricity from renewables by 2030, and such technical solutions are key to meeting that goal. Other rail systems in Europe (and beyond) are watching these developments closely, with many planning similar upgrades; for instance, Deutsche Bahn’s latest sustainability report describes efforts to build new converter stations and digital control systems to handle a growing share of decentralized renewable generation feeding into its 16.7 Hz traction power grid [2], [14].

The push to integrate renewable energy into railway networks is strongly supported by international and national policy frameworks. Decarbonizing transportation is a crucial element of meeting global climate targets, and rail – being one of the most energy-efficient modes – is seen as a vehicle to drive this change provided its own energy supply is clean. The European Commission’s strategic documents (such as the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy 2020 and the European Green Deal) explicitly call for the further electrification of rail and the use of renewable and low-carbon energy in rail operations as part of achieving a 90% reduction in transport emissions by 2050 [16]. In parallel, the International Union of Railways (UIC) has been mobilizing the rail industry worldwide through initiatives like the “Low-Carbon Rail Transport Challenge” and the “Railway Climate Responsibility Pledge.” These initiatives urge railway operators to commit to ambitious targets for cutting CO₂ emissions and increasing the share of renewables in their energy mix, with the vision of a carbon-neutral rail sector by mid-century [17]. Many UIC member railways have responded by setting their own targets for 2030 and 2050 that align with these aims. For example, Japan Railways (JR) has announced plans to significantly expand solar power use at stations and rail yards, and aims for carbon-free electricity in operations in the 2030s. In the United States, Amtrak’s pledge for 100% carbon-free power by 2030 for traction is in line with broader federal goals to decarbonize the electricity sector, and is supported by policy incentives for renewable energy procurement. In India, the government’s railway energy strategy (part of its national climate action plan) not only drives renewable installation but also has led to innovative financing models, such as solar tenders specifically designed for railway consumption and bilateral agreements with solar developers. In summary, there is a converging consensus among policymakers, industry groups, and railway companies on the importance of integrating RES into rail networks – it is both an environmental imperative and, increasingly, a smart economic choice as renewable electricity becomes the cheapest form of new power in many regions.

For all the progress to date, it is also recognized that significant challenges remain in implementing these innovations at full scale. Upgrading legacy railway power systems to accommodate renewable generation and storage can require substantial capital investment and careful engineering to avoid disruptions. In many places, pilot projects have proven technical feasibility, but scaling up will demand systemic changes – a coordinated approach to planning energy and rail infrastructure together, new regulatory frameworks that perhaps allow rail operators to participate in energy markets (selling excess renewable energy or providing grid services from railway storage, for instance), and robust standards for safety and interoperability of all these new components. At present, the introduction of RES into railway power supplies is often happening in a somewhat piecemeal fashion: a solar plant here, a battery installation there, or one rail line powered by a special PPA, and so on. To maximize benefits, these efforts will need to be integrated into a holistic energy strategy for rail networks. This entails developing what was referred to in one analysis as a new hierarchy for traction power supply, incorporating elements of smart grids, distributed generation, and advanced control algorithms as fundamental building blocks rather than add-ons [15], [17]. Encouragingly, the trend is moving in this direction – rail infrastructure managers and energy providers are increasingly collaborating on “energy master plans” for rail corridors, assessing renewable resource availability, grid connection points, and storage needs in a unified way. Furthermore, experience from initial projects helps refine the business case: railways are learning that renewable integration can yield not just environmental benefits but also operational cost savings in the long run (for example, solar power often has lower levelized cost than grid electricity in sunny regions, and capturing braking energy reduces overall consumption). There are also reliability benefits, as localized generation and storage can keep trains running through grid outages or reduce the strain on aging grid connections.

Here, the argument shifts from what makes renewable-based railway power technically viable (power-electronic interfaces, reversible substations, ESS for regenerative braking, and ICT/ML-enabled forecasting and dispatch) to *how* those capabilities are actually scaled in real systems. In practice, deployment trajectories are determined less by any single device class and more by the surrounding policy, market design, and institutional capacity that convert promising pilots into system-level outcomes. Two archetypal pathways have emerged. The first is a market-oriented model in which railways act as sophisticated corporate buyers and system participants—contracting long-term PPAs, certifying guarantees of origin, co-investing in storage, and monetizing flexibility and ancillary services while progressively hardening traction

networks with VSC converters and digital control. The second is a state-coordinated model in which rail electrification, renewable build-out, and grid expansion (including HVDC/UHV backbones) are planned as an integrated program, enabling direct coupling of remote renewable bases to high-demand corridors and urban rail, with standards and financing aligned from the outset.

Against this background, Europe and China provide the clearest real-world laboratories. Europe demonstrates how liberalized power markets, EU-level climate law, and utility-scale contracting can lift renewable shares in the traction mix quickly—while targeted substation upgrades and wayside storage safeguard power quality. China, by contrast, illustrates how central planning and ultra-high-voltage transmission can synchronize explosive growth of wind and solar with the world’s largest electrified railway network, including on-site PV at major stations and dedicated links to traction supply. The following sections therefore examine these two contexts in detail—not as competing narratives, but as complementary toolkits for translating technical readiness into durable, scalable decarbonization of railway power.

The International Union of Railways (UIC) has played an important role in supporting these initiatives through international frameworks. The Railway Climate Responsibility Pledge, launched at COP21 in Paris, urged railway operators worldwide to commit to reducing CO₂ emissions, increasing energy efficiency, and integrating renewables [17]. Most major European railway companies, including DB, SNCF, NS, ÖBB, SBB, and PKP, have signed this pledge, embedding renewable energy targets in their corporate strategies. The UIC also provides a platform for benchmarking and knowledge exchange, allowing railway companies to compare their performance and share best practices in renewable integration.

The alignment of EU policy, corporate strategy, and financial instruments has been a decisive factor in Europe’s success. The European Investment Bank (EIB) has identified railway electrification and renewable integration as priority areas for climate lending, providing dedicated financing mechanisms [18]. Moreover, the European electricity market’s liberalization has enabled railway companies to act as large corporate buyers of renewables, driving investment in new capacity through PPAs and guarantees of origin. These institutional and market features explain why Europe has emerged as the global leader in renewable-powered railways.

China, in contrast, follows a state-driven model aligned with its national climate and energy strategies. In September 2020, President Xi Jinping announced that China would aim to peak carbon emissions before 2030 and achieve carbon neutrality by 2060 [19]. This commitment has far-reaching implications for all sectors of the economy, including transport and railways. With more than 40,000 km of high-speed rail and

over 100,000 km of electrified track, China operates the largest electrified railway system in the world. The electricity consumption of this network is immense, making it a significant factor in the country's energy transition.

China's approach to renewable integration in railways is multifaceted. At the systemic level, the decarbonization of the national grid ensures that the electricity used by railways becomes progressively cleaner. By 2022, China had installed over 750 GW of renewable capacity, and the government's target for 2030 is to exceed 1,200 GW of combined wind and solar capacity [20]. Since railways draw electricity directly from the national grid, the greening of the grid translates into reduced carbon intensity of train operations.

At the project level, China has initiated direct renewable integration into railway infrastructure. Photovoltaic panels have been installed on the roofs of major railway stations such as Beijing South, Hangzhou East, and Shanghai Hongqiao, providing clean electricity for both station operations and traction substations [21]. In 2023, the first dedicated solar farm designed to power a railway section was commissioned, marking a new stage in direct renewable integration. Wind energy projects have also been considered along railway corridors, especially in the northern provinces where wind potential is high.

A distinctive feature of the Chinese strategy is the integration of railways with ultra-high-voltage direct current (UHV DC) transmission systems. These corridors transport renewable electricity from the resource-rich western regions to the industrialized eastern provinces. Some high-speed railway lines are designed to connect with UHV DC infrastructure, allowing them to be powered by remotely generated renewable electricity [22]. This reflects a highly centralized planning model, where the expansion of renewable generation, transmission infrastructure, and railway electrification are coordinated at the national level.

Urban rail systems in China are also embracing renewable integration. Metro networks in Beijing, Shanghai, and Shenzhen have installed rooftop solar panels and battery storage systems to reduce reliance on fossil-fueled electricity [23]. The Ministry of Transport's Green Transport Development Guideline (2021–2035) explicitly calls for expanding renewable energy use in rail transit, underlining the role of urban mobility in the national carbon neutrality strategy [3].

When comparing Europe and China, it is evident that both regions have prioritized renewable-powered railways but through different governance models. Europe relies on market mechanisms, corporate responsibility, and EU-wide policy alignment, while China follows a top-down planning model that integrates railways into national energy strategies. Both approaches are effective in their respective

contexts: Europe demonstrates how liberalized markets can empower railways to drive renewable investment, while China illustrates how centralized planning can synchronize railway electrification with massive renewable deployment.

Despite these differences, the convergence is clear: both Europe and China see railways as critical components of their decarbonization pathways, both are investing in advanced technologies such as storage and power electronics, and both are embedding renewables directly into railway infrastructure. These parallel experiences provide complementary lessons for other regions: the importance of aligning railway policy with national energy strategies, the role of innovative financing mechanisms, and the value of both centralized and decentralized approaches to renewable integration.

Translating the global experience into a context of sustained disruption requires reframing integration of renewables from a purely decarbonization exercise into a resilience-by-design program. The comparative review of Europe and China shows two complementary pathways: a market-oriented model that uses liberalized power markets, corporate power purchase agreements, guarantees of origin, and certified carbon-free portfolios to green traction electricity; and a state-coordinated model that plans electrification, renewables, transmission, and control systems as a single program, with converter-rich substations and storage embedded from the outset. Both converge on the same technical core—modern power-electronic interfaces, energy storage at traction nodes, and digital control with reliable communications—but they differ in sequencing and governance. These lessons map directly onto the Ukrainian case, where the rail system must continue operating under wartime conditions while simultaneously cutting emissions and costs. A purely market solution is insufficient if upstream assets are damaged; a purely centralized build-out cannot react fast enough to local outages. The practical answer is a hybrid: use market tools to clean the upstream portfolio where feasible and, in parallel, harden the traction network locally with distributed renewables, storage, and converter-based nodes that can form islanded microgrids when required.

Ukraine's starting point is both challenging and enabling. The network is among the largest in Europe, with roughly 47% of route length electrified and the majority of traffic already moving under the wire. Electrification is predominantly 3 kV DC, with 25 kV 50 Hz AC on selected corridors. The power system has been synchronized with Continental Europe, opening pathways for clean electricity contracting, cross-border balancing, and future participation in flexibility markets. At the same time, repeated strikes on generation and transmission, plus constrained access to capital equipment, impose strict boundary conditions on design and rollout. In this environment the

strategic value of rail–energy-efficient, mass-capacity, geographically distributed—makes it the ideal platform for a resilience-first integration of renewables. The national research effort reflects this pivot: the Zaporizhzhia National University project on innovative solutions for integrating renewables into the railway power network explicitly targets Ukrainian traction realities, anchoring laboratory work to field constraints and ensuring methodological compatibility with European standards and practices [24]. The role of such domestic R&D is not to repeat international studies, but to translate them into actionable designs for 3 kV DC corridors, dispersed substations, and mixed rolling-stock fleets, and to codify protection, control, and operating procedures suitable for wartime reliability targets.

A coherent Ukrainian roadmap therefore links three layers. The first is grid-facing decarbonization: leverage synchronization to procure certified low-carbon electricity through corporate PPAs and structured portfolios, while preparing regulatory interfaces for storage and demand-side services so that traction assets can support system balancing when conditions allow. The second is traction-embedded generation and storage: deploy photovoltaic plants and, where feasible, wind at depots, yards, stations, and along rights-of-way; pair them with containerized battery energy storage at traction substations sized to capture regenerative braking, buffer short-term renewable variability, and ride through upstream disturbances. On DC sections, prioritize reversible substations capable of exporting to and importing from the public grid; on AC sections, prefer VSC-based feeders that provide harmonic mitigation, fast voltage support, and bidirectional control. The third is digital and protection modernization: establish a secure SCADA/EMS layer with edge analytics that forecasts train power demand from timetables, gradients, and rolling-stock characteristics, and forecasts renewable output from weather nowcasts; coordinate set-points for converters, storage, and protective devices; and rehearse black-start and resynchronization procedures for islanded operation of priority nodes. Across all layers, design choices should reflect wartime constraints: physical hardening and dispersion of assets to reduce single-point vulnerability, modular equipment that can be swapped rapidly, dual-path communications with local autonomy, and cybersecurity engineered into converter-rich architectures. Financing and institutions complete the picture. Donor support and climate-aligned lending can be targeted to “critical-node microgrids” where the resilience benefit is immediate and measurable; standardized interconnection and protection rules will allow private partners to co-develop substation-adjacent solar-plus-storage; and portfolio contracts can be structured to hedge seasonal variability while local storage delivers operational continuity. Crucially, pilots must be designed to become standards rather than one-off

demonstrations—documenting engineering data, protection settings, and operating procedures, and feeding them back into national technical specifications and training. In sum, the logic of the global transition points toward a Ukrainian pathway that blends market procurement with programmatic engineering, couples renewables and storage directly to traction nodes, and elevates digital control and protection to first-class design variables. This is not only compatible with long-term climate goals; it is the most practical way to keep trains moving, safely and reliably, in the face of shocks—turning the railway into both a backbone of low-carbon mobility and a resilient spine of the national energy system.

Ukraine’s rail sector is entering a decisive phase of its energy transition under the most adverse conditions imaginable: a wartime operating environment marked by repeated strikes on energy and transport infrastructure, constrained access to capital and equipment, and the need to maintain a critical lifeline for the economy and society. Yet, precisely because railways are inherently energy-efficient and electrification-ready, integrating renewable energy sources (RES) into the traction power system offers a high-impact path to simultaneously decarbonize, lower operating risks, and harden resilience. In this context, it is essential to emphasize that such research is not only being carried out globally, but also in Ukraine itself. Zaporizhzhia National University (ZNU) is conducting dedicated work under R&D No. 0125U002117, “Implementation of innovative technical and technological solutions for the integration of renewable energy sources into the railway power network,” which directly addresses the Ukrainian traction power system and its specific constraints and opportunities. The official registration card of this project confirms the scope and topicality of the research agenda, anchoring it within the national R&D system and providing a formal basis for subsequent technical development and piloting [24].

To ground the discussion, several structural characteristics of Ukraine’s railway and energy systems are salient. First, Ukraine operates one of Europe’s largest rail networks (~19,800 km), of which roughly 47% is electrified—placing the country among high-electrification systems, but with substantial room to extend catenary or deploy clean traction alternatives on diesel corridors. Importantly, this electrified share carries a dominant portion of passenger and freight traffic, making the energy profile of traction power a strategic lever. Official statistics and multilateral assessments converge around an electrification ratio of ~47–47.5% in recent years, with absolute electrified length near 9,900–10,000 km [25]. Second, since March 16, 2022, Ukraine’s power system has been synchronized with the Continental Europe Synchronous Area (ENTSO-E). This emergency synchronisation—subsequently regularized with increasing commercial exchange capacity and the completion of key compliance steps

in 2023—fundamentally re-framed options for clean electricity sourcing, system stability, and cross-border balancing, all of which are relevant for rail traction procurement strategies and railway-adjacent RES projects [26].

The wartime context sets binding boundary conditions. From spring 2024 through winter 2024/25, Russia intensified systematic attacks against electricity generation and transmission assets, complicating secure supply for traction loads, amplifying volatility, and heightening the value of distributed, island-capable resources near critical rail nodes. Authoritative assessments from the IEA and the UN Human Rights Monitoring Mission document the escalation and scope of damage to energy infrastructure and the societal risks it creates [27]. Rail-specific impacts have included targeted strikes and attempted disabling of traction power substations—episodes reported repeatedly since April 2022 (e.g., the Krasne traction substation in Lviv Oblast) and in renewed waves in 2025 that caused widespread service delays while sparing passengers through effective operational response [28]. Under these conditions, technical pathways that combine on-site renewables, energy storage, grid-forming converters, and advanced digital control can enhance both decarbonization and continuity of service.

A rigorous literature view—international and Ukrainian—converges on several implementation pillars for integrating RES with railway power systems:

Direct and indirect renewable integration at scale. Mature railway operators in liberalized markets often combine indirect integration (contracted green power via PPAs/guarantees of origin) with direct physical integration (on-premise PV/wind tied into traction substations or feeder stations). Case studies across Europe show that PPAs can anchor multi-hundred-GWh annual supply portfolios, while direct coupling increases local resilience and can reduce losses. For Ukraine, ENTSO-E synchronisation opens additional procurement and balancing avenues, enabling corporate PPAs and cross-border hedging strategies as the market framework evolves [26].

Converter-based, reversible traction substations and power-electronic interfaces. A consistent theme in railway power research is the centrality of modern power-electronic interfaces—VSC-based converter stations, reversible DC substations, STATCOM/SVC, and modular multilevel converters—to manage bidirectional flows, stabilize voltage under variable RES injection, and filter harmonics. Steimel’s seminal work on power-electronic supply of AC railway systems remains a canonical reference for the shift from transformer-centric architectures to converter-rich topologies that support distributed generation and storage [14]. For Ukraine’s dominant 3 kV DC

corridors, reversible substations and DC-side storage are particularly relevant to harvest regenerative braking, smooth PV variability, and improve power quality.

Energy storage as a reliability and efficiency core. International practice has moved from pilot to deployment of traction-side storage (lithium-ion, supercapacitors, and hybrid configurations) sited at substations or along feeders. Storage increases the capture of regenerative braking energy, cushions RES variability, and supports islanding in contingency modes—capabilities that become critical under wartime disruptions. A well-documented regional exemplar is Poland’s PKP Energetyka: the 5 MW/1.2 MWh traction battery at Garbce (3 kV DC) demonstrably stabilizes voltage, increases renewable self-consumption, and provides backup for critical sections—exactly the multi-service model that Ukrainian traction operators can adapt [29].

Digital forecasting and smart-grid ICT. Integrating intermittent RES with moving traction loads requires high-fidelity forecasting (train power demand from timetable/operations, PV/wind output from weather nowcasting) and distributed, low-latency control across substations. The industrial informatics literature emphasizes IoT-enabled monitoring, distributed optimization, and resilient communication architectures for grids with high DER penetration—concepts that transfer directly to traction power networks as they adopt converter-based nodes and storage [15]. In Ukraine’s case, digital twins of traction sections, cyber-secure edge controllers at sectioning posts, and adaptive protection settings under variable short-circuit levels should be part of any RES-integration roadmap.

Policy alignment and system planning. The adoption of Ukraine’s National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) in June 2024 and the Energy Community’s 2024 Implementation Report provide a strategic anchor for RES deployment, flexibility assets, and market reforms. The NECP’s renewable and efficiency targets, combined with ongoing EU alignment, establish a regulatory pathway for corporate procurement, connection codes, storage participation in ancillary services, and distributed generation programmes—all enabling conditions for railway RES integration [29]. Advanced modelling work for a resilient, decentralised system through 2030 further highlights the near-term system value of distributed PV and storage, while warning about flexibility constraints and curtailment if deployment is not coordinated with balancing resources—insights that are directly actionable for siting RES at or near traction nodes [30].

Against this background, the Ukrainian traction power system presents a distinctive engineering canvas. The network consists predominantly of 3 kV DC electrification (with 25 kV AC on selected axes), a topology inherited from historical development and tuned for heavy freight and long distances. Integrating RES here

implies: (a) substation-level coupling of PV (and where feasible, wind) on the MV/HV side with DC link support through reversible converters; (b) wayside storage dimensioned for regenerative peaks and short-term PV smoothing; (c) voltage support via static power conditioners/STATCOM functions to maintain EN 50163 compliance under intermittent generation; and (d) islanding modes that allow critical rail nodes to ride through grid disturbances. These measures mirror international practice but must be adapted to Ukraine's current reliability envelope and operational hazards.

The literature already contains Ukrainian-authored contributions addressing many of these issues. Recent peer-reviewed work by Ukrainian and regional co-authors [31] synthesizes global technologies for railway-RES integration—covering traction and non-traction loads, interconnection criteria for distribution networks, and mitigation of power-quality problems introduced by inverter-based resources and storage. The article underscores the strategic role of storage and advanced control in railway contexts similar to those in Central-Eastern Europe [31]. Complementary Ukrainian research streams (e.g., earlier engineering work on DC traction, solar coupling, and protection coordination) provide a body of design patterns—valuable when translated into wartime constraints such as mobile substations, rapid reconfiguration, and component scarcity.

A realism test in today's conditions is resilience. The IEA's 2024 analysis stresses that intensified attacks since spring 2024 have left the system fragile, making *distributed*, quickly deployable assets a priority [27]. For rail, that translates into siting PV and storage inside the railway estate (depots, yards, stations, traction substations), with islanding capability and black-start support for signalling and switching gear. While some emergency generation financed for Ukrzaliznytsia (UZ) since late 2024 is thermal and focused on continuity (small-scale dispatchable units), these assets can later pivot to balancing variable renewables as market rules and grid conditions normalize—echoing the broader policy thrust towards flexibility and DERs [32]. In parallel, synchronisation with ENTSO-E enhances the feasibility of clean PPAs (including cross-border) and access to regional balancing capacity, reducing the variance of renewable-heavy supply portfolios for traction power [26].

Comparative lessons from Europe and nearby systems map well onto Ukraine's needs. Poland's rail energy programme demonstrates that containerized BESS at 3 kV DC substations can materially improve voltage stability and renewable utilization; Germany's converter-dominated 16.7 Hz system shows how power electronics can absorb large shares of RES without compromising railway-specific power-quality constraints; and ENTSO-E integration frameworks illustrate how interconnections and market tools complement local hardware. The policy dimension is equally important.

Ukraine's NECP and Energy Community guidance point to auctions with contracts for difference, reform of grid codes for inverter-based resources, and enabling ancillary-service markets—all necessary for rail-adjacent PV/wind + storage projects to scale beyond pilots [29].

From a systems-engineering standpoint, three design choices stand out for near-term Ukrainian pilots under R&D No. 0125U002117. First, prioritize substation-proximate PV (1–10 MW blocks) plus 2–10 MWh BESS with black-start capability, coupled through reversible DC traction converters; this maximizes regenerative capture, improves ride-through, and creates microgrid potential around key nodes. Second, deploy predictive, secure ICT layers (edge-based forecasting of train demand and PV output, adaptive set-point control for converters and BESS, cyber-hardened comms) to orchestrate DERs at millisecond-to-minute scales; the industrial-informatics literature provides mature control templates for such distributed environments [15]. Third, embed resilience-first protection and operations: dynamic protection settings under variable short-circuit levels, supply-islanding procedures for stations and interlockings, mobile spare assemblies (containerized rectifier-inverter sets), and modular spares for fast restoration when hardware is damaged. These measures are not only compatible with decarbonization—they make it more operationally feasible in wartime.

Finally, market and institutional alignment will determine pace and scale. With ~47% electrification and a large traction load, UZ is a systemically significant electricity off-taker. In the ENTSO-E era, UZ can accelerate decarbonization by (i) contracting carbon-free electricity via PPAs (domestic and cross-border where feasible), (ii) co-developing substation-adjacent PV/BESS assets with independent power producers under standardized interconnection and revenue-stacking rules, and (iii) participating in flexibility services where regulation allows (voltage support, fast frequency response from BESS, contingency support). In parallel, donor-backed programmes can prioritize critical-node microgrids for rail hubs, combining resilience finance with clean-energy objectives—an approach already recommended in multiple system-level studies of Ukraine's post-2024 electricity sector [30].

In sum, Ukraine's railway decarbonization is feasible even under wartime constraints if framed as a resilience-driven RES integration project: converter-centric traction interfacing, substation-proximate PV and BESS, predictive ICT for secure operations, and policy frameworks that unlock bankable procurement and ancillary revenues. The ongoing ZNU research (R&D No. 0125U002117) speaks directly to these priorities and can serve as a technical backbone for pilots that demonstrate not just lower emissions and cost, but the ability of a modernized traction power system to

withstand and recover—keeping trains running on clean energy when the country needs it most [24].

Electric railway transport has a number of advantages compared to other types of transport, the main of which are: relatively less pollution of the atmosphere, better adapted for the transportation of significant weight and number of passengers, has a controlled schedule. However, for the organization of reliable functioning of railway transport, it is necessary to have the appropriate infrastructure (traction and contact network, track management, rolling stock, etc.).

In recent decades, there have been certain changes in the organization of railway transport, which are primarily related to the introduction of high-speed transportation, environmental friendliness and increased energy efficiency. The developed situation is primarily related to the understanding of the need to save energy resources and reduce the impact on the environment. New means of electricity production based on renewable energy sources (RES) actively help in solving the problem.

The development of electricity production using renewable energy sources (RES) in European countries has a steady upward trend. According to the latest statistical data presented in the report of the authoritative agencies Agora Energiewende and Ember, in 2020 a "historical event" took place, namely the share of electricity generated from RES amounted to 38%, overtaking the amount of electricity from fossil fuels - 37 % (Fig. B1) [2].

Fig. B1. Percentage share of electricity production in Europe from various sources for 2010-2020 (Source [2])

If we consider the statistics of electricity production from RES in European countries for 2010-2020 according to the data of the European Commission (Fig. B2), we can conclude that the ambitious goal, which was achieved by the countries of the European Union, of producing 20% of RES energy by 2020 has been achieved [2].

Energy from renewable energy sources

(%, share of total gross final energy consumption, 2010 and 2020)

Fig. B2. Share of energy from renewable sources in 2010 - 2020 (% of gross final energy consumption) (Source [2])

Based on the above trend, it becomes clear that the share of RES will continue to increase, gradually expanding the scope of application. One of the promising directions for the use of RES is their application in the structure of railway transport. According to [11], the scope of application of RES in the structure of railway transport can also be: objects of railway transport in regions with unstable power supply; "transport and energy corridors", i.e. places where railway and road routes are combined; high-voltage transmission lines and communication lines; autonomous objects of the infrastructure of railway transport, as well as problematic places of the traction power supply structure with the standardized indicators of the electric energy quality, primarily voltage deviations and asymmetry.

The development of efficient electrical energy storage systems using RES, in addition to reducing CO₂ emissions, allows to significantly improve electricity quality indicators, to ensure the construction of more efficient systems with re-use of regenerative braking energy to the maximum possible extent. An important element in the functioning of this system is also ensuring the efficient operation of traction substations, which are the main source of power for electrified railway transport facilities. The main task to ensure the further development of such systems is to find

new ways to maximize the use of RES in the existing structure of railway transport [12].

The specified direction of work corresponds to the provisions of the European Energy Strategy of Railway Transport for the period until 2030 and the National Transport Strategy of Ukraine for the period until 2030. Other areas of use of RES systems include the following:

- feed the traction power system from the external network, in which, alongside traditional systems, RES also works;
- connection of RES to the windings of traction transformers, from which non-traction consumers of railway power line are directly powered;
- use of alternative energy in booster points to strengthen the traction line;
- connection of RES located in the railway exclusion zone directly to the contact line from which both traction and non-traction consumers receive power;
- use of RES as a source of local power supply systems for specific non-traction consumers with the possibility of feeding them from the traction network.

The construction features of the traction power supply system countries vary significantly, therefore the conditions for the optimal use of RES of various nature are determined by a set of optimality criteria and a system of restrictions (quality of electric energy, cost of electricity, etc.). The result depends on specific tasks during the implementation of the project. It should be noted that the use of one or another of the specified directions of the RES introduction into the railway power supply systems is still chaotic and unsystematic and requires the solution of a complex of issues. The problematic issues include the development of a new hierarchy of the traction power supply structure based on the technologies «intelligent networks» (Smart grid) [1], energy storage systems (ESS) [33] and control algorithms in conditions of the stochastic nature of RES [14].

CHAPTER 1 INFLUENCE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES ON POWER QUALITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE TRACTION POWER SUPPLY SYSTEM

1.1 Current state of development of traction power supply systems

The process of using electric energy to ensure transportation on railways took place over a long period of time and is associated with certain features of technical progress. According to the data shown in tab. 1, it is possible to see the degree of railway electrification in the world at the end of 1990 [34] (Table 1).

Table 1 State of electrification in 1990 (Source [34])

Country	State of electrification, %
Denmark	7
Germany	42
Switzerland	99
Europe (on average)	37
USA	1
Soviet Union	36
South Africa	36

After thirty years (data for 2020), the situation in some European countries looks as follows [35] (table 2)

Table 2 State of electrification in 2020 (Source [35])

Country	State of electrification, %
Switzerland	100
Poland	59
Germany	55
France	53
United Kingdom	34

From the given data, it can be concluded that the total length of the railway power supply system is constantly increasing and this trend will continue in the future. The evolutionary development of such systems led to the conception of five main types: on direct current - 750 V, 1500 V and 3000 V, and on alternating current - 15/11 and 25 kV with operating frequencies of 16²/₃/25 Hz and 50/60 Hz, respectively. Long experience of the operation of the specified systems have shown their rather high efficiency at operating speeds up to 250 km/h and lack of significant problems in operation.

However, recently, the concept of the development of high-speed European railways network has appeared. Table 3 shows the conditional lengths and relative share of four traction power supply systems of different types (2003) [36].

Table 3 Network line lengths and share of electrical railway systems (2003)
(Source [36])

Network characteristics	Length, km	Length, %
DC 1500 V	15320	6,5
DC 3000 V	72105	30,3
AC 15 kV/16 ² / ₃ Hz	32390	13,6
AC 25 kV/50 (and 60) Hz	106437	44,8
Others	11350	4,8
Total	237600	100,0

The existing diversity of railway electrification systems in European countries can be seen in fig. 1.1 [13].

Fig. 1.1 Railway main power supply systems in Europe. (Source: [37])

It should also be noted that the development and use of these systems was conditioned by the state of scientific and technical progress at that time period [34]. Thus, in the alternative current system, the use of a frequency of 16.7 Hz was associated with the use of collector motors, which were excited by alternating current of reduced frequency. The reduction in frequency was provided by the use firstly mercury and then thyristor rectifiers together with DC motors with pulsating current, that is, the AC system underwent constant improvement. The direct current system, on the contrary, from the initial moment of its use has practically not changed, with the exception of a gradual increase in the value of the supply voltage to a certain level.

The railway power supply system consists of two systems: traction power supply and power supply of non-traction consumers. The traction power supply system is the central element of the traction power supply system and consists of a system of traction substations, a system of generation and storage of electrical energy (if available), and a contact line. Fig. 1.2 shows an example of such a structure.

Fig. 1.2 Example of the structure of the traction power supply system. (Source: own study based on [38])

The traction power supply system can have two structures of electrical energy distribution: centralized and decentralized [36]. In the case of using a centralized system (Fig. 1.3), the catenary line is connected by an intermediate link, which is

powered by dedicated railway power plants or the general network, while in decentralized systems, the catenary line is connected directly to the general network.

Fig. 1.3 Examples of hierarchical structures of the railway power supply system:
a) centralized; b) decentralized (Source: [36])

As shown in fig. 1.3, in a centralized system, the catenary is powered by special traction substations, which in turn receive electrical energy directly from the power system, while in a decentralized system, the catenary line is connected directly to the utility network.

The formation and development of centralized systems took place at the beginning of the process of railway electrification due to the need to use a reduced

frequency in the catenary network. In the process of development of power conversion technology, there is a gradual development of decentralized systems, which have become dominant today in most European countries, with the exception of Germany, Austria and Switzerland, where historically centralized topology was used earlier. A characteristic feature of the decentralized system is the ability to use distribution networks in parallel with the catenary network or to have in its structure generation or storage systems that are directly or indirectly connected to the catenary network [37].

The advantage of the direct current system is the ability to effectively use decentralized systems with means of distributed generation, which provides the opportunity to apply high voltage direct current.

Disadvantages of the DC system:

- due to the low voltage in the traction network, a higher EMF consumption current (electricity losses ~ 22%);
- in the case of significant current loads, the distance between traction substations is 20 km or less, which causes the high cost of the power supply system and high operating costs;
- large current loads require the use of a contact suspension of a larger section, which is accompanied by significant overspending of scarce non-ferrous metals, and at the same time, mechanical loads on the contact network supports increase;
- intensive corrosion of underground metal structures, including catenary network supports, occurs when direct current electric traction is applied.

Advantages of the AC traction power supply system:

- increasing the voltage in the contact network to 25 kV reduces the load current, voltage and power losses;
- increased distance between traction substations (up to 40-60 km) and reduced their number (two-three times);
- reduced construction period;
- lower costs of non-ferrous metals.

Disadvantages of the AC traction power supply system:

- asymmetric mode of operation of three-phase transformers and, as a result, worsening of the quality indicators of electrical energy and a significant decrease in their available power;
- non-sinusoidal nature of consumed currents, as well as deterioration of the quality of electrical energy in the power supply system (the consumed current curve contains negative higher harmonics);
- AC traction network is a source of electromagnetic influence on adjacent devices, including communication lines;

- the presence of equalizing currents, and therefore, additional large losses of electrical energy.

The system of providing electrical energy to railway consumers has a rather complex and extensive structure. The main functional elements of which are traction substations (ECHE), sectioning points (PSK) and parallel connection points (PPZ), etc.

Examples of the implementation of AC ECHE power supply schemes, PSK and PPZ are shown in Figures 1.4 and 1.5.

Fig. 1.4 Simplified schematic diagram of alternating current ECHE (Source: [39])

The main consumers of electrical energy at the traction substation are consumers located mainly at railway junctions, sorting district stations, etc. The most powerful consumers are the objects of the locomotive and wagon industry (approximately 50...60% of the installed capacity within the road section).

Fig. 1.5 Schematic diagram of power supply of PSK and PPZ in the direct current power system (Source: [39])

Figure 1.6 shows a typical load profile for one of the traction substation during the day.

Fig. 1.6 Load power (time interval – 1 min.) (Source: [40])

The system of own needs (SON) at the traction substation

In general, SON can be presented for an AC (Fig. 1.7) and DC (Fig. 1.8) substation.

Fig. 1.7 Generalized scheme of own needs on ECHE of alternating current (Source: [40])

Fig. 1.8 Generalized scheme of own needs on direct current ECHE. (Source: own study based on [38])

In the general case, the own needs of traction substation consist of the following consumers: circuit breaker heating devices (if necessary), switchgear; electric lighting and heating of premises. Power supply to responsible consumers is provided through the guaranteed power bus, others – through the non-guaranteed power bus.

Figures 1.9 and 1.10 shows the power profile for own needs registered on DC and AC traction substations (Figs. 1.9 and 1.10).

Fig. 1.9 Consumed active a) and reactive b) power for own needs of the AC traction substation

Fig. 1.10 Consumed active a) and reactive b) power for own needs of DC traction substation. (Source: [41])

The structure of SON of traction power supply facilities has certain features: consumers are divided into responsible and non-responsible.

The first group includes communication devices, a network of guaranteed electric lighting, devices for ventilation and heating of battery room premises, devices for pumping fuel, oil and water to ensure long-term operation of the automatic diesel generator (ADG). All consumers of this group receive power from external sources of alternating current, and in the event of an accident - from the ADG.

The second group includes the network of general lighting, ventilation equipment, power equipment of workshops and other auxiliary premises. Consumers of this group receive power from external sources of alternating current, and are turned off in case of damage.

Consumers of the first group belong to electrical installations of category I of a particularly important group. They must be supplied with electricity from two independent power sources and an interruption in their power supply can be allowed only for the time of automatic switching on of the backup power (no more than 1.3 s). In addition, for such electricity consumers, it is necessary to provide additional electricity supply from a third independent source. At the electrical centralization stations (ECS) of large stations, a diesel DGA or (and) storage batteries are used as a backup source.

Due to the fact that various devices with pulsed power supply units have become widely used recently, there is a danger of information loss by these devices, or their complete failure.

There is also a modern tendency to reduce the power consumption of SON, on the basis of more energy-saving equipment (LED lamps, microprocessor relays, modern high-voltage switches, etc.). Since the self-locking line receives power from its own needs, when introducing high-speed traffic and using new types of rolling stock with power electrical equipment and pulse-width modulation (PWM) of the traction current, problems arise with ensuring electromagnetic compatibility and quality of electricity in the power supply networks of the information and control systems of train traffic control, which can adversely affect the safety of train traffic.

Consideration of the main components in the structure of the railway power supply system allows us to determine the possibility of using RES on various elements of the system. An important factor affecting the effectiveness of the implementation of such systems is the analysis of the degree of influence of electric energy quality factors that affect the reliability of railway power supply systems and allows determining their further development prospects.

1.2 Indicators of electrical energy quality and reliability in the traction power supply system

A feature of the direct current traction power supply systems is the usage of a large number of high-power converting devices, due to which the study of electric energy quality issues, as in the case of all non-linear loads in electrical systems, remains a relevant and important problem in electric traction systems. It is known

about the usage of uncontrolled rectifiers at traction substations, the number of pulses of which is determined by the windings of the traction transformer and the configuration of the static converter [42], [43]. Common schemes are 6-pulse [44], [45], 12-pulse [46], and even 24-pulse diode rectifiers [47] (Fig. 1.11). The application of thyristor-based controlled rectifiers in traction substations (TS) came much later, in order to take advantage of DC voltage control, fault current limitation, and improved performance in terms of speed, reliability, and lower energy losses, as well as the ability to increase the distance between traction substations [48]. The development of controlled rectifiers allowed the usage of reversible devices that had the ability to recover electricity into the network. Despite the wide spread of insulated gate bipolar transistors (IGBT) in powerful converters, when choosing rectifiers based on them, it is necessary to take into account their significantly higher losses and cost compared to thyristor-based rectifiers [49]. The schematic solutions in fig. 1.11 illustrate the simplified structure of conventional DC traction substations based on six-pulse and twelve-pulse parallel/serial uncontrolled rectifiers and the corresponding waveforms of phase voltages and currents. Due to the presence of rectifiers, the main problem is the harmonic distortion of the current from the AC side, unlike in AC traction systems, where the main problem is the unwanted level of asymmetry.

The level of harmonic distortion is high, especially since the number of pulses of the rectifier is smaller. The range of total harmonic distortion (THD) vary approximately from 10 to 30% in the absence of compensation measures [50]. Achieving the level of current harmonic distortion below the well-known limit of 5% provided by the IEEE-519 standard [51] is the main goal of applying compensation measures. Even if the pull-up rectifiers are diodes, there is also a small amount of reactive power that must be compensated. It is worth mentioning that if THD (which calculates the ratio of the distortion component to the fundamental frequency component I_1) stays within the limit, then the total demand distortion (TDD) as defined by the standard – computed by dividing the distortion component by the maximum current consumption I_L – will also remain within the limit, given that I_L consistently exceeds I_1 [52].

Figure 1.11 Simplified schemes of the usual DC-traction substations and specific waveforms of the supply phase current and voltage: (a) case of 6-pulse uncontrolled rectifier and (b) case of 12-pulse parallel and series uncontrolled rectifier (Source: [53])

An effective mean of reducing the impact on quality of energy in the DC traction power supply system and solving the task of maintaining the appropriate value of the voltage deviation (at the level of 5%), according to IEEE Std. 141-1993 [54], is usage of active power filters (APF). This measure allows achieving high performance in terms of full compensation of the influence of higher harmonics, reactive power and even asymmetry, but it is too expensive. A cheaper option is usage a parallel connection called a shunt active power filter (SAPF), the principle of which is based on the structure of a voltage source inverter (VSI) (Fig. 1.12a). Moreover, due to the hybrid structure consisting of passive filters and SAPF, the advantages of both types of filters are used with lower costs (Fig. 1.12b). Examples of the use of SAPF and a hybrid structure (SAPF and a passive filter tuned to the 5th and 7th harmonics) on DC traction substations are given in [55].

In a three-phase alternating current system, characteristic quality indicators are: voltage deviations and fluctuations, the presence of asymmetry, the influence of higher harmonics (HV), reactive power, etc. According to the established limits noted in the IEEE-519-1992 standard (last updated in 2014) [51], the most important indicators in the field of electric transport are the reverse sequence current, the level of higher harmonics of voltage and current, and the value of reactive power [56]. Currently, two classic approaches have been formed for improvement of the quality of electric energy, namely: the development of efficient power supply systems with

the introduction of system modeling [57], [58], [59] measurement, analysis and calculation of system parameters [60], [61] or improvement of technical means, which allows to reduce the negative influence of HV indicators [62], [63], reverse sequence current [64] or all factors at the same time [65], [66].

Fig. 1.12. Structure of shunt active feed compensator (SAPF) used in DC substations: (a) simple SAPF and (b) hybrid compensator (Source: [53])

For a more complete understanding of the causes of these phenomena, it is necessary to analyze their causes and means of reducing their negative impact.

Asymmetry of current and voltage. The asymmetry of current and voltage in the traction power supply system is the most serious problem, due to the fact that most trains are single-phase, and since the traction load has a fairly significant level (for example, 5–20 MW), it can cause significant damage to the power system and should be compensated accordingly. The most common measure to reduce asymmetry is the method of phase shift using special transformers [64], the use of which allows reducing the negative consequences, although it leads to an increase in the cost of the entire system. In some cases, static volt-ampere reactive compensators based on constant capacitors/thyristors, controlled reactors or capacitors with thyristor switching have become widespread. The most advanced in this field are the solutions given and include one or two shunt converters to compensate the total inactive components of the current. An effective measure to compensate the asymmetry is also the use of a two-phase system [65], [66].

Higher harmonics. The widespread use of 12-pulse rectifiers in the DC power supply system leads to a significant level of 11th and 13th harmonics, and for AC traction systems, trains use AC/DC/AC converters, which causes harmonics of various orders to enter the three-phase power system, compensation methods for their reduction/elimination are proposed and studied in [62], [67]. The classical method of

HV reduction was usage of passive filters [62] and specially connected transformers, which can also be used as passive filters, reducing the impact of HV depending on the type of transformer and their order [67]. An effective method of reducing the impact of HV remains the control of AC/DC/AC converters of traction motor drives in trains [68]. Thus, three-phase rectifiers can convert alternating power supply into direct current, and then inverters with the help of transformers provide power to the consumer, in the form of a three-phase induction or synchronous motor/generator.

The most effective measure to reduce the impact of HV is the use of active shunt filters, but these filters are quite expensive. A better option would be usage of certain combinations of active and passive filters (to reduce the speed of the active filter). In addition, the auxiliary power source of the train consumes a low-frequency harmonic current, for which the compensation method is investigated in [69].

Reactive power. Modern AC converters of traction motors use PWM, which generates zero reactive power, and for power quality compensators the power factor is also equal to 1 [70]. Previously, single-phase collector motors were used; however, for the past 50 years, single-phase rectifiers/three-phase inverters have relied on a combination with three-phase synchronous or asynchronous machines (motors/generators) that return energy to the single-phase power system during regenerative braking, where the rectifier becomes the inverter and the inverter becomes the rectifier [71]. Nevertheless, the capabilities of a PWM rectifier with respect to bidirectional power flow and near-unity power factor in both rectification and braking modes were reviewed in [72]. At traction substations, the generation/transmission of reactive/active power is required to compensate the asymmetry. Accordingly, such systems must be in anti-phase with three-phase currents/voltages to eliminate reactive power. Thus, reactive power compensation and asymmetry compensation are not performed separately.

Changing the supply voltage. The most common problem with ensuring the appropriate voltage level is deviation from the normalized value. As already mentioned, the presence of asymmetric current causes the appearance of asymmetric voltage. According to the IEC-6850 and EN-50163 guidelines, traction motors and other loads in trains can operate with a 24% reduction in voltage amplitude value or a 10% increase in voltage amplitude from the nominal value, which does not interfere with the operation of the system.

The presence of an electric arc. Due to the specifics of providing electrical contact between the receiver of electrical energy and the contact network, the phenomenon of electrical arcing occurs, which is directly related to the dynamic width tolerance between the wheels and the rail [73]. This phenomenon affects the quality

of the voltage and current curve and generates a transient constant component in alternating current systems, which can sometimes cause dielectric breakdown.

The graphs in Figures 1.13-12 are examples of indicators of the quality of electrical energy.

Fig. 1.13 Voltage level in the self-demand system of the traction substation of direct a) and alternating b) current (Source: [41])

a)

b)

Fig. 1.14 Voltage asymmetry coefficient by reverse sequence in the self-demand system of a traction substation of direct (a) and alternating (b) current (Source: [41])

a)

Fig. 1.15 The coefficient of voltage sinusoidal distortion in the self-demand system of a traction substation of direct (a) and alternating (b) current (Source: [41])

The influence of quality indicators on the level of electrical energy losses. The indicator of electricity losses is one of the most important indicators of the efficiency of the electricity supply system, accounting and activity of energy supply organizations. Power losses of up to 10% are considered physical. All energy losses in the network can be divided into main (productive) and additional (unproductive). The main ones include losses arising from the provision of electric energy to consumers of rolling stock. Losses due to the presence of reactive power spillovers, low-quality electricity, etc. can be attributed to additional ones [74]. According to [74], power losses in the traction substation and network elements amount to 5-20% of the active power of the rolling stock (depending on the location of the electric locomotive). Total losses in the traction network can reach values of 28– 35%.

The influence of indicators of the quality of electrical energy on the operation of systems. As a result of the deterioration of the quality indicators of electrical energy, the power source of the network is most affected, which can be seriously damaged. In addition, it can significantly harm the operation of the railway's signaling and communication system. The impact of low-quality electricity of traction systems on is mentioned in [73], [75], such indicators of the automation system as stability of operation, reliability, safety, capital and operating costs depend significantly on the quality of electric energy. According to the statistics of failures in power supply devices of stations under the influence of external factors (for example, atmospheric overvoltage), 6.1% of failures occur in the power supply panels of the CHP post, due to the influence of traction currents of railways with electrified direct and alternating current - 9.2%.

Impact on signaling and communications. Track circuits are designed to work with a special frequency that should not create obstacles for the power supply frequency. However, in the presence of harmonics, communication signals can be affected by harmonic frequencies [73], [75], resulting in false signals and incorrect positioning of the train, which lead to a disaster. Communication cables, in turn, usually run parallel to power cables. In the presence of stray currents, the catenary current and the reverse current will not be equal to each other, due to which the equivalent magnetic field in the communication cables will not be zero, and in turn will induce voltage in the communication cables and interfere with communication signals. Moreover, high-order harmonics can cause interference to communication in power systems.

Briefly, the influence of various factors on the indicators of the quality of electric energy in the electric traction system, and the means for their minimization, are shown in Figure 1.16.

Figure 1.16 Classification of the strategy for improving the quality of electricity. (Source: [56])

The further development of traction power supply systems is under the influence of many factors, which include increased requirements for speed, operational efficiency, service safety, environmental friendliness, etc.

New trends of influence on indicators of the quality of electric energy by means of distributed generation

The considered indicators of the quality of electrical energy allow to determine the degree of influence of RES systems on them. A practical result can be the use of the generated electrical energy to ensure regulation of the DC supply voltage at the traction substation [76], [77], [78]. The ability of the photovoltaic plant inverter to

generate reactive power can be used to reduce its impact on the traction power supply system and increase the power factor of the entire system [79].

In recent years, the application of smart grid technology in traction power supply systems is an urgent issue of improving the environmental friendliness of railway transport in the USA, Europe and Japan, for example, the East Japan Railway Company considers it a future necessity [76]. Photovoltaic systems with multi-level step-up converters can be implemented to reduce energy costs and improve the reliability of power systems.

1.3 The degree of use of renewable energy sources in the traction power supply structure

RES make it possible to build local systems of distributed generation (DG), which significantly change the hierarchy of traction power supply systems. The most widespread RES systems are solar power plants (SPP), built on the basis of photovoltaic energy conversion, and wind power plants (WPP), which use wind energy. The vast majority of hybrid systems consist of these types of power plants due to their greater versatility compared to other energy sources. According to some researchers [80], as an alternative source of energy, micro-hydro turbine installations can be used, their high economic efficiency has been proven, but their use is very limited by the geographical features of the area.

The following groups can be identified among the possible options for the introduction of RES into the rail transport electrification system by type:

- power generation systems based on photoelectric converters;
- generation systems based on wind power stations;
- hybrid generation systems.

Depending on the region and climatic conditions of the area, it may be economically viable to use systems based on a single energy source or a combination of several sources. According to the report [81], the use of solar energy conversion systems is relevant for countries such as India, Saudi Arabia, Egypt and Argentina, but not for Northern European countries such as Sweden, Norway and Finland. At the same time, some regions with low solar radiation can use wind energy quite efficiently. As a rule, these are countries with coastal territories and highlands or states located near the Arctic Circle. According to the recommendations of the International Union of Railways [82], it is possible to determine the following options for the placement of renewable energy sources on railway transport facilities, presented in Figure 1.17.

Fig. 1.17 Classification of RES sources for rail transport electrification systems (Source: [12])

Based on the location of the RES system according to Figure 1.17, they are divided into two types:

- systems located on rolling stock;
- stationary renewable energy systems.

The most common type of systems on rolling stock is the placement of photovoltaic converters on the roof of the train [83], which is especially relevant in southern countries such as India [84], Ethiopia [85], Malaysia [86], etc., precisely because of the high level of insolation in these regions. Systems located on rolling stock have smaller dimensions, cost and, accordingly, less power. They are simple and convenient to operate, do not require frequent maintenance due to the absence of moving parts, they can be installed horizontally on the roof, with minimal changes to the aerodynamic properties of the train.

The work [87] proposed the use of compact wind generators (WT) of low power with a vertical axis of rotation of the rotor with a nominal power of 3.6 kW for installation on the roof of the car, similar in design of the generation system are given in [88], [89]. However, such a decision may cause an increase in the coefficient of frontal resistance of the train, which will lead to an increase in the power consumption of the main traction engines. In addition, the presence of moving parts in the wind turbine mechanism requires periodic maintenance and repair.

Stationary systems of renewable energy, unlike systems on rolling stock, allow to significantly increase the amount of "green" energy generation, which is due to the absence of restrictions on their scaling for large areas and the use of proven structures.

Options for such systems are the following:

- wind turbines with a vertical axis of rotation installed along the railway;
- wind parks for railway electrification;
- photoelectric converters on the roofs of stations and the surrounding area;
- solar farms for railway electrification;
- application of hybrid wind-solar power generation systems.

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the use of the specified systems, it is necessary to analyze them.

Wind turbines with a vertical axis of rotation installed along the railway

Installation of wind generators with a vertical axis of rotation along the railway makes it possible to effectively use the air flow that occurs when a train passes near the turbines. A feature of generators of this type is a lower operating threshold in terms of rotation speed. Unlike wind generators with a horizontal axis of rotation, these generators have a minimum speed of 1.5-2 m/s, and enter the nominal mode of operation at a wind speed of 10-12 m/s, which is especially important in conditions of weak wind and when using a wind turbine of the flow created by the movement of the train [90], [91], [92]. The power of generators can vary depending on the model and dimensions in the range from tens of watts to tens of kW, however, the number of installed wind turbines is limited only by the length of railway tracks and the topography of the area.

The effectiveness of these installations directly depends on the density of train traffic through the considered section of the railway track. According to the simulation results given in [91], 10 WT Kliux Zebra with a nominal power of 4 kW are able to generate 32.3 MWh during the year, similarly in [90] 10 WT with a nominal power of 1.8 kW located in a tunnel along the route trains, provide the possibility of producing 79.83 MWh during the year.

As already mentioned above, the unit power of WT of this type does not exceed several kW, which requires the installation of a large number at a considerable distance along the railway track. The local connection of each individual installation to the overhead line through a converter is technically difficult and expensive, since the nominal voltage of the WT does not exceed 1000 V AC, and the nominal voltage of the overhead line can reach 3-24 kV DC or AC. A centralized connection scheme, at one or more points, will require the laying of a large number of cable lines along the tracks, which will significantly affect both the amount of capital costs and the level of losses in the power transmission lines on the way from the generator to the final consumer. This option is convenient for consumers of low power located at a small distance. For example, for lighting systems or signal lamps on different sections of the railway track.

Wind farms for electrification of railways

The variants of WT systems with a vertical axis of rotation described above are used in small-scale wind power generation (up to 100 kW wind turbines). However, the auxiliary systems of trains and railways are not the only application of wind energy. The connection of large wind farms with powerful WT with a horizontal axis of rotation makes it possible not only to meet the needs of the railway and household consumption, but also to provide energy to such a powerful consumer as the electric traction system. Such a decision will allow not only to reduce the consumption of electricity from the power system and thus to reduce pollution, but also to improve the quality of electricity due to the compensation of voltage fluctuations on long intersubstation sections. The fact [93], [94], [95] of the positive impact of wind turbines, which is characterized by an increase in voltage in communication nodes, and a negative impact on the quality of electricity and general harmonic distortions in the system, is known. The power of connected wind turbines can vary from a hundred kW to tens of MW. It should be noted that for the efficient operation of large WT in the region, average annual wind speeds must be sufficiently high. Coastal and mountainous areas are considered the most successful areas for installing wind turbines, such experience is given in projects of integration of large-capacity wind farms (up to 20 MW) with the railway power supply system [96]. WT can be connected to the railway electrification system through substations in the vicinity of railway stations, but it is most optimal to install additional power plants in the inter-substation zones of the railway at the same distance from the substations. This will significantly reduce power and voltage losses in overhead lines and ensure greater energy efficiency of the railway, reducing the likelihood of power shortages in the rolling stock. It should be noted that wind farms above 1 MW often operate in parallel with the power grid, while smaller capacity systems are used as part of hybrid microgrid systems together with other types of RES and energy storage. The application of hybrid systems in railway transport will be considered in more detail in the following sections.

Photoelectric converters on the roofs of stations and the surrounding area

SPP based on photovoltaic converters is the most versatile option for RES because, unlike micro-hydroelectric power plants, photovoltaic converters are less dependent on the energy source and can be placed anywhere and on almost any surface. At the same time, they have no rotating parts, unlike WT, which greatly simplifies their operation and increases reliability.

A very effective solution is the installation of photovoltaic panels on the roofs of railway stations, canopies over platforms, openings between railway tracks,

soundproof and windproof walls, roofs of repair depots and traction substations. This allows you to avoid the alienation of a large plot of land for the construction of a solar station and ensures the location of the energy source in close proximity to consumers who are residential consumers of the station. Many developing countries (India, Pakistan, Vietnam, Malaysia, Turkey, etc.) and developed countries (Australia, Germany, Japan, etc.) design and implement photovoltaic systems at railway stations [86], [34], [97]. The experience of China in implementing photogeneration systems at "Beijing South railway station" and "Hangzhou East railway station" [98] and Japan is interesting. According to [99], the total capacity of photovoltaic plants on the roofs and adjacent areas of railway stations in Japan exceeds 100 MW. The power range of individual photovoltaic complexes varies depending on the size of the station and the place for placing the photovoltaic modules on its territory, from 5 kW on the roof of the Settu-Shi platform to 453 kW at the Tokyo station. Since solar panels have to be placed on the roof of buildings in a horizontal position or at a non-optimal angle to the sun, the efficiency of such plants can be reduced compared to solar plants of similar power, but located in an open area.

The location of photo modules above the railway bed or along the land adjacent to the railway track between stations is also one of the options for effective use of the territory at the disposal of the railway company during the construction of the SPP. In [96], [98], [100] examples of installation of photovoltaic modules along railways are given. However, this way of placing photovoltaic cells creates similar difficulties with connecting the installations to the overhead line, as for WT in the previous section. Since photopanel need to be cleaned from dirt and dust, it should be noted that the location of photocells at a long distance makes their maintenance difficult.

Use of solar farms for railway electrification

The use of photo panels connected in a specially designated area for a large-capacity solar power plant (from several hundred kW to tens of MW) leads to alienation of significant areas, but has its advantages, namely:

- photopanel are at an optimal distance from each other at an optimal angle and can be additionally equipped with solar trackers for constant adjustment of the angle of inclination;
- [power transmission losses are reduced due to their compact location](#);
- simplified maintenance of photopanel;
- the solar plant can simultaneously provide high power to compensate for the power and voltage imbalance in the overhead line.

Today, the use of powerful solar stations to power the overhead line of trains is a common practice in many countries with a high level of insolation, examples of such systems are given in [96], [98], [101].

Large SPPs with a capacity of megawatts can be a source of energy for energy-deficient nodes and sections of the railway, where significant voltage drops are observed during the passage of rolling stock of significant mass. However, as in the case of WT, a serious disadvantage of SPP is the non-uniformity of electricity production depending on the time of day and cloudiness. To ensure the appropriate level of reliability of electricity supply to consumers, it is necessary to have a significant power reserve in the power system, which significantly reduces the effect of using such systems. The solution to the noted problem is the development of hybrid systems, including generation systems based on RES, as well as different types of RES.

Application of hybrid wind-solar power generation systems by rail transport

The development and implementation of microgrid systems based on Smart Grid technologies in railway electrification systems allows solving a number of current problems, such as:

- increasing the voltage level and bandwidth in remote areas of the network;
- reduction of costs for the purchase of electricity during periods of peak electricity consumption;
- reduction of CO₂ emissions by increasing the share of electricity production from RES.

The main areas of development of such systems are:

- choosing the optimal configuration of electricity generation and storage systems at the design stage;
- development of an algorithm for optimal control of microgrid modes during operation.

The solution of the first problem is given considerable attention in the works of many authors, for example, in [40] the main problems of RES in railway transport systems are discussed. The main disadvantage of such systems is variable mode of operation and significant fluctuations in output power. On short time intervals (from seconds to minutes), this problem is more typical for WT, on longer ones (hours, days) — for SPP. The negative impact of these factors can be reduced by joint use of WT and SPP due to the fact that the peak electricity production of these plants does not coincide on a daily interval, which allows to avoid significant interruptions in electricity supply. The works [80], [34] provide an analysis of various RES sources and suggest their best combination with SPP in a microgrid system. It has been shown

that in most cases, the combination of several energy sources allows for increased system efficiency, reduced energy storage costs, and more stable system operation.

The search for the most effective control algorithms for hybrid microgrid systems has received considerable attention in the publications of various authors [102], [103]. In work [104] proposed a method and algorithm for controlling a hybrid system based on the power maximization criterion. Control is carried out through reversible converters, which ensure the connection of alternating current and direct current systems into a hybrid system. Special attention is paid to the stability of the microgrid system during transient processes caused by a sudden change in load or output power from RES. It should also be noted that the efficiency of the microgrid system strongly depends on the efficiency of the control system. It is the search for optimal methods and algorithms for managing a complex system consisting of a large number of different subsystems and elements that is given the greatest attention in the works of most authors studying the hybrid microgrid system. A huge role in the operation of RES is played by the choice of SPP configuration. This system can be implemented using one type of RES or a hybrid of several that use different physical principles.

Since the flow of power between the structural units of the system is regulated by changing the opening angle of the thyristor, the lack of time delay when changing the mode can lead to sharp voltage drops. In work [105], the laws of controlling converters in a hybrid system were developed. In [106], a solution to the problem of flexible mode control using algorithms is proposed, a strategy based on fuzzy logic using a genetic algorithm is considered. Based on the above, it can be concluded that the use of microgrid systems based on several RES sources is in most cases a more efficient energy supply option than individual types of RES operating in parallel with the external power system. This solution makes it possible to compensate for the shortcomings of each individual energy source through the integrated use of generation, energy storage, regenerative braking and energy flow management technologies. The power range of such systems can vary from several hundreds of kW to tens of MW, which makes it possible to use them both for powering stations and for auxiliary systems of railway substations and for powering the electric traction line. However, the construction of these systems requires significant capital investments.

Substations can be controlled as DGs, and the advanced single-phase traction grid can be considered a special type of microgrid (MG). Unlike conventional MG [107], [108], traction MG has several unique characteristics. First, the locomotive load moves along the traction grid, which means that the resistance distribution of the system changes regularly. Secondly, due to the unique features of traction power

infrastructure, the distance between two substations is fixed at tens of kilometers, which leads to the effect of line impedance, which cannot be ignored. Thirdly, in contrast to DGs of different power, converter substations with the same power are connected to the traction network. Automatic power distribution should be implemented in response to line impedance change [109], which is different from proportional power distribution in conventional MG [110], [111]. Finally, since the traction power system is an autonomous AC system, the AC traction MG constantly works in autonomous mode [112]. Coordinated operation between multiple DGs in the context of autonomous MG operation is often discussed in the literature. Conventional island MGs contain several inverter-based DGs that are installed in parallel [113]. Depending on the control objectives, there are three typical control modes, namely P/Q control, V/F control, and droop control [114]. Under P/Q control, the DG inverter operates as a current source whose output power is command-dependent. In contrast, a fixed voltage and frequency reference are accepted by the inverter for V/F control. In the improved single-phase system, only one contact line is used, which does not require a neutral section. All substations are connected to a single-phase alternating current traction network [115]. Inspired by the MG concept, the MG single-phase AC traction section is offered here. The topology of the system is schematically presented in Figure 1.18.

As shown in Figure 1.18, substations are used to stabilize the traction network and supply locomotive loads. The traction MG and the main network are interconnected by substations through AC-to-AC converters (SS1 and SS2). Compared to a conventional transformer, a converter-based substation operates as a controlled voltage source with better controllability. Due to the characteristics of a single-phase AC traction MG, the substation converter always operates in stand-alone mode. The distance between substations is usually a kilometer (km), and the influence of line resistance (LL1, LL2 and LL3) is negligible. In addition, the capacity of each substation is identical, which is different from the case in a typical MG, where the generating capacity will be different. In the traction MG, only the locomotive load is represented. Loads are not connected at fixed points during train movement.

Figure 1.18 Single-phase AC traction microgrid (PV - photovoltaic) (Source: [116])

The line resistance between the source and the load is constantly changing, and therefore power distribution between substations is difficult to achieve with a conventional droop controller. Based on the change in line impedance, an automatic power distribution strategy can be adopted. The locomotive load will be automatically connected to the nearest substation. This method is not only easy to use, but also constantly maintains the operating voltage of the loads in an acceptable range. In addition, DGs can also be directly connected to the traction network. The energy produced by DG can be used to support loads or feed into the grid through a substation. Without any neutral section, the DG is also more flexible to connect to the traction belt. As a result, the proposed traction MG will help with renewable penetration along the railway.

1.4 Evaluation of the effectiveness of models and optimization of modes with sources of distributed generation of different configurations

The available power of RES-based generation systems, primarily SPPs and WPPs, depends entirely on weather conditions and is classified as stochastic generation. Ensuring the balance of active power leads to underutilization of the

available RES capacity when it is in excess or to limit the load when it is in short supply. ESS provides the most optimal process for the integration of RES into electrified railway systems, allowing the processes of production and consumption of electrical energy spread over time. The smoothing of the RES output power with ESS is achieved by storing energy during periods of high generation and producing energy for use when the RES output power is reduced due to weather conditions. In this case, the ECS must respond to changes in accordance with the rate of oscillations and have a sufficient reserve of energy to operate in the range from several minutes to several hours.

Since the operation of powerful wind and solar power plants as part of the national energy system has certain regulatory and legislative regulation, the easiest way would be to integrate these power plants into the general network. In this way, the electricity supply of railways would not depend directly on the operating modes of RES, their stochastic nature would be compensated by the capabilities of the general energy system. However, taking into account the significant share of electricity consumption for transport needs, as well as the dispersion of railways and the presence of dowry territories, it would be appropriate to consider the independent use of RES. In this case, a group of WPPs or SPPs together with a consumer (structural element of railway transport) can be considered as a local energy system. It can be defined as a set of generating electrical equipment of limited capacity, converters and consumers of electricity, interconnected taking into account the topology of the distribution network, in which single electromagnetic processes occur. At the same time, the condition must be fulfilled:

$$\Sigma P_{sp}(t) = \Sigma P_{gene}(t) \quad (1.1)$$

In this case, variable generation and their energy consumption should be considered as a single process. At the same time, the share of energy consumed from the general network decreases, while the requirements for balancing the local network increase. A natural requirement for the construction of a combined energy system based on renewable energy sources is the minimization of the uncontrolled dispersion of the energy balance as the difference between the values of generated and consumed power. Since the stationary component of generation and consumption can be predicted and provided for by the scheduled work schedule, there is a need to estimate precisely the random component of power fluctuations. The data source for such an assessment can be a record of the actual values of generation and consumption, formed as a time series.

The actual data of wind speed, solar radiation and actual consumption, which is the actual load for the power system, are chosen as information for the study of real

operating modes and their mathematical modeling. In this example, the load schedule at the AC traction substation (Poltava South) in winter time is used, and the weather data refer to the central region of Ukraine for the same time of year. At the same time, it is considered that short-term (less than an hour) fluctuations of generation and consumption are independent random variables, which is verified by the authors. As evidenced by the analysis of statistical data, the operation of WPPs and SPPs is characterized by the presence of some average power and a random component, which are functions of time. Average power can be considered well predicted for the short term, and considered a controllable parameter. The expression for determining the power balance will have the form [117]:

$$p_{ij} = (a_{ij} - a_i) - [(w_{ij} - w_i) + (s_{sj} - s_i)], \quad (1.2)$$

where a_x is the level of electricity consumption; w_x and s_x – capacity of wind power plant and SPP, respectively; i – time index (time interval number); j – number of the day, p_{ij} – deviation from the load schedule.

RES indicators with one index are averaged for a certain hour of the day (the so-called daily course), in particular, *and must* correspond to the planned schedule of consumption, then $p_i = a_i - w_i - s_i$ corresponds to the planned so-called "clean" load. The choice of the length of the time interval (Δt) is determined by the features of the energy source – for wind turbines, the characteristic time of changes is usually taken to be equal to 10 min., for SES – up to 1 min., and short-term load changes can have a second dimension. The available meteorological data make it possible to estimate the power of typical wind turbines and SPPs in conventional units or in fractions of the nominal (maximum achievable) power, and the load can be described in the same way. Examples of typical modes of power change are shown in fig. 1.19.

Figure 1.19 – Daily course of solar radiation (maximum achievable and actual). (Source:Own study)

The choice of an elementary time interval is determined by the properties of the object under study, namely the rate of change of a characteristic parameter. If processes of different variability are compared, they should be brought to the same time interval. At the same time, a change in the length of the interval causes a change in the dispersion of the time series values. When enlarging the scales of averaging, the rule is used that the variance of the general population is the sum of the inter-interval variance and the average value of the intra-interval variances: $\sigma^2 = \sigma_0^2 + M\{\sigma_k^2\}$, where σ_0^2 – dispersion of average values in each interval, σ_k^2 is the variance on the k th interval, M is the symbol of mathematical expectation. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the number of intervals should provide an acceptable statistical error, and the general population can be considered to be such a long process, during which its main properties will be sufficiently manifested. Since the critical factor of the RES system is the variability of the balancing process, a differentiated (in finite differences) series is considered, the elements of which are the difference of successive power values: $dp_{ij} = p_{(i+1)j} - p_{ij}$. A difference series of this type can be constructed both for the total power balance and separately for the generation and load components: $da_{ij}, dw_{ij}, ds_{ij}$.

The distribution of random variables in the obtained series corresponds to the hypothesis of normality. Since the obtained series of successive power changes (fluctuations) can have a large spread, it is worth screening out random extreme outliers, for example estimating the range of possible values with a confidence probability of 0.99 and 0.95, discarding one and five percent of the sample, respectively. The analysis of the actual indicators of power fluctuations in conventional units when the spread range for various components of the power system is increased when the time step is increased (change in the elementary time interval Δt) and reduced to the corresponding nominal power (extreme, confidence intervals, standard deviations σ_d) is shown in Fig. 1.20.

From the comparison of the indicators of the variability of power changes, it can be seen that with the increase in the length of the time interval Δt , the range of fluctuations is expected to increase. The increase in variance is non-linear, bounded from above, and the range of changes depends significantly on the size of the confidence interval, and decreases significantly when several extreme values are discarded. Own load changes at the same time intervals have greater relative values than RES power changes (Fig. 1.20, horizontal scale is non-linear).

Dispersions of the current power values of the components of the local power system have different relative values; the variance of the total power balance should be defined as the sum of the covariances of the components taking into account their weighting factors. Similarly, the variance of the difference series, which characterizes the rate of changes in the power balance, is determined:

$$D\{dp_{ij}\} = D\{da_{ij}\} + wD\{dw_{ij}\} + sD\{ds_{ij}\}, \quad (1.3)$$

where w , s are weighting factors that determine the share of WPP and SPP capacities, respectively. Mutual independence of power fluctuations is taken into account here.

Figure 1.20 – Standard deviations of power changes depending on the time interval.

(Source: Own study)

For example, if the nominal capacities of WPPs and SPPs are equal to each other and equal to the maximum load capacity, then the normalized standard deviation of power fluctuations at an averaging interval of 10 min. Will increase from 0.23 (without RES) to 0.25. Similarly, with an averaging interval of 30 min. increase in deviations from 0.25 to 0.30. This is the potential increase in the standard deviation of current changes in the power balance. Knowing the standard deviation, you can determine the confidence intervals of the current power fluctuations with a given accuracy. The nature of the distribution of these fluctuations as a random variable is quite reliably described by the normal (Gaussian) law (Fig. 1.21).

It should be borne in mind that in this example, the weighting factors reflect the nominal power of RES, while the effective (or averaged) power indicators are much smaller. So, for wind turbines, the nominal capacity utilization factor is within 0.3-0.4 depending on the location and season, for SPPs it is usually 0.14-0.18. This

fact should be taken into account when calculating the energy contribution of RES. Economic components are determined by standard means [118]. Instead, it is the current power changes that are important to ensure stability and reliability.

Figure 1.6 – Histogram of current changes in the power balance.

(Source: Own study)

The second indicator in the creation of mathematical models is the representation of energy curves by power functions and further operations on them. All schedules of loads and generation, for their further use, must be specified by functions. The extremes of the curve (graph) are determined graphically (Figure 1.22).

Figure 1.22 – An example of a graph and its extremes.

(Source: Own study)

Next, the curve is divided into the number of extremum minus one sections. The extreme points of the section are the two extremes closest to each other. The equation of the curve of each section is determined by the formula:

$$\begin{vmatrix} x^2 & xy & y^2 & x & y & 1 \\ x_1^2 & x_1y_1 & y_1^2 & x_1 & y_1 & 1 \\ x_2^2 & x_2y_2 & y_2^2 & x_2 & y_2 & 1 \\ x_3^2 & x_3y_3 & y_3^2 & x_3 & y_3 & 1 \\ x_4^2 & x_4y_4 & y_4^2 & x_4 & y_4 & 1 \\ x_5^2 & x_5y_5 & y_5^2 & x_5 & y_5 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

where $(x_1; y_1)$, $(x_2; y_2)$, $(x_3; y_3)$, $(x_4; y_4)$, $(x_5; y_5)$ are the points that lie on this section of the curve. At the same time, two of them are the extreme points of the studied area.

Equation (1.4) will be valid only if three of the given points lie on the same straight line, and if no four of them lie on the same straight line. Each function that was determined by formula (1.4) will correspond to a certain section of the main graph (Figure 1.23)

Figure 1.23 – An example of a graph that consists of several functions.

(Source: Own study)

According to Figure 1.23, each function has its definition range.

The next step is to find the sum of all load schedules:

$$(f+g+\dots+i)(t)=f(t)+g(t)+\dots+i(t) \quad (1.5)$$

Similarly, the total energy schedule for generating plants is determined. After defining the functions that describe the two main energy graphs (generation and

consumption), the model calculates their difference and produces a characteristic graph. An example of finding the difference between two energy curves is shown in Figure 1.24.

To simplify the example, each graph in Figure 1.24 is described by one function. In a real case, the number of functions that describe the energy curve can be much more, depending on the number of objects (consumers and generators) and the curvature of the energy graphs of each of the objects. According to Figure 1.25, the difference of two functions is mathematically written as:

$$(f-g)(t) = f(t) - g(t) \quad (1.6)$$

The resulting graph $(f-g)(t)$ is shown in Figure 1.25. This curve $(f-g)(t)$ is offered as the final result of the model. Based on this schedule, it is possible to draw conclusions about the shortage or excess of electrical energy at a certain time, and make a constructive decision about introducing a new source of energy or disconnecting the load at a certain time.

Figure 1.24 – Basic energy graphs of consumers and generators. (Source: Own study)

Figure 1.25 – Resulting energy graph. (Source: Own study)

Also, the expert may change the load indicators of consumers (if this is provided by the project). After adjusting the input data, the model calculates everything from the very beginning and gives the corresponding result, which can be compared with the previous one. The example shows calculations of the operation of the electricity supply system during the year. The model can perform calculations for shorter periods of time, however, due to the large amount of information uncertainty, the accuracy of such calculations will decrease in proportion to the reduction of the time interval.

Comparative analysis of renewable energy system configurations

Unfortunately, choosing a universal configuration that most fully meets the needs of railway companies in all situations is not possible due to too many factors influencing the decision. Depending on the climatic features of the region, the maximum allowable cost, the availability of free space for the installation of the installation, the requirements for the reliability of the system, etc. In each specific case, the use of one or another option of the power supply system will be effective; therefore, the final choice is always made on the basis of a technical and economic comparison of configurations within the framework of the project being developed.

The table shows eight RES options used for the electrification of railway transport:

1. Mini-WT on the roofs of cars;
2. WT with a vertical axis of rotation along railway tracks;
3. Wind farms on local railway sections;
4. Photocells on the roofs of cars;
5. Installation of photocells on the roofs of railway stations, platforms, overpasses, linear pillars, soundproof walls;
6. Installation of photocells along railway tracks;

Based on the review, the following recommendations can be formulated:

1. RES systems located on the roofs of cars are suitable for providing the train's own needs. In countries with a high level of insolation, the best option is to place solar cells on the roofs of the cars. In countries with a low level of insolation, the option of using WT can be considered. The power of one installation usually does not exceed 1 kW; however, their number can vary from a few pieces to several dozen pieces, depending on the length of the train.

2. To meet the needs of electric receivers on the railway track (lighting, signal lamps, etc.), it is possible to use WT with a vertical axis of rotation. The power unit, depending on the WT design, can vary from 1.5 to 5 kW; however, it is possible to

increase the capacity of the system by installing another number of hydroelectric plants along the railway line.

3. Placing solar panels along the railway and on special canopies can also be an effective option to meet the railway's own needs. The throughput of such a system, as practice shows, is limited only by the length of the railway track. Currently, the construction of systems with a nominal capacity of more than several hundred kW is associated with high capital costs. The situation is similar with the placement of photocells on the roofs of train stations and platforms.

4. In the near future, a significant improvement in the characteristics of electrical energy storage systems (significant energy capacity, very good charge/discharge speed, and reduced overall dimensions) is expected in the near future, with corresponding competitiveness, which can significantly affect the development of energy storage systems in various designs. At the same time, the ability of the photovoltaic inverter to generate reactive power is used to reduce the impact of connected photo modules on the traction power supply system and increase the power factor of the entire system.

5. If the previous options were considered through the prism of reducing railway consumption and replacing a share of electricity consumption from the system, then the construction of large wind turbines and solar power plants with a capacity of several MW to several tens of MW. allows to ensure the production of a sufficient amount of electricity to power the aerial railway, as well as to regulate the voltage on the energy-deficient sections of the railway, the most distant from the power substations.

6. The most effective option from the point of view of reliability and quality of power supply is hybrid microgrids, which include various generation systems based on RES, as well as various types of SPP. The presence of an energy storage allows you to avoid large power outages and more efficiently overcome consumption peaks. However, the effective functioning of these systems is impossible without the development and implementation of algorithms capable of automatically selecting optimal control strategies for dynamically changing railway consumption schedules.

CHAPTER 2 DISTRIBUTED GENERATION SYSTEMS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACCUMULATION SYSTEMS IN THE TRACTION NETWORK

2.1 Calculation methodology and structure of the complex energy hub, taking into account the local RES potential

The optimal ratio of individual elements in combined energy systems based on RES is determined taking into account many important factors, namely: availability of traditional energy sources; climatic (meteorological) conditions; the structure of energy supply and energy consumption systems; requirements for the quality of electrical and thermal energy; requirements for the energy supply schedule; environmental and economic factors, etc. A feature of local energy systems is the need to optimize the composition of generating capacities and their characteristics, modes of compatible operation. Such optimization should take into account the specifics of energy consumption, requirements for the reliability of supply, the available potential of renewable energy sources (solar, wind), and cost indicators. A natural requirement for the construction of a combined power system based on renewable energy sources is the minimization of the uncontrolled dispersion of generated power values while maximizing the energy produced. In the economic formulation of the optimization problem, the role and weight of the average RES power and root mean square deviation (RMS) are different, it is determined by the cost of electricity and means of reserve and/or accumulation, but the best result is provided by the presence of both criteria.

The need to estimate precisely the random component of power fluctuations follows for various reasons [119]. A significant introduction of RES, if it is not accompanied by sufficient energy storage, will require balancing the current fluctuations of generated energy. Sufficient reserve will be required to regulate the frequency and ensure reliable supply in case of rapid changes in generation or load. The balance of electricity consumption and frequency regulation are the main technical problems in energy systems with a significant level of implementation of wind and solar energy.

Methodology of calculation and complex energy node taking into account the local RES potential

In order to achieve high technical and economic indicators in the application of renewable energy sources, stable operating parameters of energy equipment and reliable energy supply to consumers, combined electric power systems (CEES) are being created, where electric energy can be produced and accumulated by combining renewable energy sources with traditional energy technologies. Thus, the combination

of photovoltaic panels and wind power plants not only increases the total output energy, but also smoothes the generation mode, reducing the relative magnitude of random fluctuations. A feature of local energy systems is the need to optimize the composition of generating capacities and their characteristics, modes of compatible operation. Such optimization should take into account the specifics of energy consumption, requirements for the reliability of supply, the available potential of renewable energy sources (solar, wind), and cost indicators [120].

In general, optimization problems can be divided into three groups: deterministic, incomplete information and stochastic problems. The presence of wind and solar power plants, which depend on the weather, introduce uncertainty into the operation of CEES. The level of consumption is also, as a rule, random (within certain limits), therefore, the optimization of such CEES should be stochastic. Recursive analysis methods are also used to evaluate its work, using historical data on wind speed, solar radiation and the nature of consumption. In such a setting, the problem of optimal capacity selection is completely deterministic, and its solution is usually reduced to linear programming methods. In addition, recursive analysis allows you to calculate the parameters of the mathematical model and control its adequacy [121].

Since the generation performance is directly proportional to the nominal power, which is determined by the number of individual elements (generating modules) when the type of generation is selected, the optimization problem is an integer linear one, where the optimization parameters are the number of modules of each type. The type of module is characterized by its energy characteristic, which plays the role of the equation of state, and the constraints in the form of inequalities relate to the general parameters of the power system (network throughput, consumer needs, accommodation possibilities, etc.). When replacing productivity indicators with their mathematical expectations, i.e. moving to the averaged values of wind speed and insolation level, this problem becomes deterministic and in the majority of studies this is how it is solved. It should be noted, however, that not only the average value of the wind speed is important for wind energy, but also the dispersion, taking into account the significantly non-linear energy characteristic of WT [120].

The choice of a specific solution method depends on the formulation of the optimization problem. Consider, for example, hybrid energy systems, which provide for the generation of electricity from wind turbines and SPPs and reserve energy storage (accumulation). It is possible to optimize the parameters of such a system, if the goal is the minimum cost of electricity, the maximum utilization of it, or the most appropriate battery capacity according to one of the criteria. Since at each moment of time the current generated power has the properties of a random value, only a

probabilistic assessment of different modes of operation with a given confidence level is possible, for example, the duration of a certain mode. Certain indicators (indices) are usually used as reliability criteria. The probable power loss index *LPSP* is often used - an indicator that reflects the probability of losing the ability to fully provide energy to the consumer's needs. A deficit situation occurs when the generated power is less than the currently consumed power, and the battery capacity has reached a minimum level. If the needs are exceeded and the battery is fully charged, part of the energy will be lost. The *EHS* index is defined as the relative share of excess energy for a certain period.

Two types of indicators (indices) are mostly considered - those used to quantify system reliability, such as the probability of loss of load or expected energy, or those used to determine the economic feasibility of design, such as life cycle cost or present value of electricity [119]. If the power system also includes traditional energy sources, the goal of optimization may be to maximally replace them with renewable sources. A comparison of the actual (measured) and calculated distribution density indicates the acceptability of the normal distribution to describe the power imbalance. The values of dimensional indices are given in the table. 2.1. 0.5 h is taken as a unit of time. (time interval of measurements), data for January and July were used, options with and without a weather forecast for a day were considered. In addition to the variable capacity of actual consumers, the conditional capacities of **WT** (W) and **SPP** (S) based on synchronous actual data on weather factors are taken into account.

Table 2.1 Adequacy indices for T1 taking into account the forecast for the day. (Source: own study)

Moon	Average power, kW	Forecast status	<i>WE, LPS</i> (T=24 hours) , kWh				
			W=0, S=0	W=200, S=200	W=200, S=0	W=0, S=200	W=100, S=100
January	1070	forecast	340	620	610	370	440
		without prog.	865	1050	1045	895	910
July	680	forecast	345	585	550	400	430
		without prog.	640	865	840	675	710

A comparison of the values of the indices calculated from the scatter parameters and directly calculated from the actual measurements indicates convergence with an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$, and the differences are not of a systematic nature.

In tasks of stochastic optimization of **CEES**, it is necessary to observe changes in the mathematical expectation and dispersion at the same time, not allowing them to

exceed the given values or allowing this to be exceeded with a certain probability. To solve this problem, models with mixed conditions (two-criteria and multi-criteria problems) are considered, which will require the establishment of a hierarchy of criteria in terms of Pareto-optimality [122].

The structure of an autonomous energy node, which is characterized by a complex energy source

In modern energy, with the increase in the share of RES, more and more attention is paid to quality indicators of energy. Since the main disadvantage of such sources as solar and wind energy is their uncontrollable variable nature, ensuring the proper quality of energy supply is possible only with sufficient "flexibility" of the energy system. Factors of flexibility include the availability of controlled energy sources, as well as the use of batteries capable of solving the problems of accumulation, storage and conversion of RES energy to ensure the stability of energy supply.

In order to achieve high technical and economic indicators in the application of RES and reliable energy supply to consumers, combined electric power systems are being created, where electric and thermal energy can be produced and accumulated by combining RES with traditional energy technologies. Thus, the combination of photovoltaic panels and wind power plants not only increases the total output energy, but also smoothes the generation mode and reduces the relative value of random fluctuations. Reliability of supply will be ensured by managed energy sources (for example, diesel generators) and storage subsystems. Elements of the power system can work in parallel, series or series-parallel modes, and the system itself can be autonomous, connected to the general network or working in both autonomous and network modes. The generalized diagram of an autonomous/network system with traditional and non-traditional energy sources, as well as energy storage, is shown in fig. 2.1.

Individual elements of such a combined energy system are modeled by their energy characteristics. The traditional model of SPP power (or photomodule) is described by the formula: $P_{PV} = \eta_{PV} \cdot A_{PV} \cdot G_t$, where A_{PV} is the area of photopanel (m²); G_t – solar radiation (W/m²); η_{PV} is the efficiency factor depending on the temperature of the module and the air.

Fig. 2.1 – Typical diagram of CEES. (Source: own study based on [120])

The wind turbine model (or wind turbine) is given by the power curve $P_w(V)$, while the wind speed V (m/s) is converted to the height of the rotor axis. As a rule, a dependency of type (1) is used:

$$P_w(V) = \begin{cases} p(V), & V \in (V_0, V_m) \\ 0, & V \notin (V_0, V_m) \end{cases} \quad (2.1).$$

The produced electricity is determined by the formula:

$$E = T \int_0^{\infty} P(x) f_x(x) dx, \quad (2.2),$$

where $f_x(x)$ is the differential function of the probability distribution of the variable x (for wind turbines it is wind speed, for solar modules it is solar radiation); $P(x)$ is the power as a function of the x coordinate; T is the total working time.

The distribution function of the energy carrier for wind is the Weibull distribution, for solar radiation – the beta distribution.

For the battery, the physical limitations are deterministic:

- $P_{Ak}^{min} \leq P_{Ak}(t) \leq P_{Ak}^{max}$ – battery charge/discharge limit;
- in addition, $P_{Ak}(t+1) - P_{Ak}(t) \leq P'_{Ak}$ is the limit on the speed of the charge/discharge process.

Instead, for the equations of state of storage batteries, not only the number of occurrences of certain power values is important, but also the sequence of generated and consumed energy values, that is, power as a random function of time. After all, only previously accumulated energy can be reused; at the same time, the permissible storage volumes are determined by the technical characteristics of the battery. Since the mode of energy supply from variable RES (solar, wind power plants) is uncontrollable, while the consumer must work within certain power limits, the requirements for accumulation must be based on a probabilistic approach.

The battery charge level of the batteries at the moment of time t , provided that the generated power exceeds the consumed power, and the charge level is below the maximum, is determined by the equation

$$C_{bat}(t) = C_{bat}(t-1)(1-\sigma) + \left(E_{PV}(t) + E_W(t) - \frac{E_L(t)}{\eta_{inv}} \right) \eta_b, \quad (2.3)$$

where η_{inv} – efficiency factor of the inverter, a η_b - batteries. Here, $C_{bat}(t-1)$ is the charge level of the battery at the previous time (the time step is considered equal to 1 u.o. or Δt); $E_{PV}(t)$ is the energy produced by the photomodule during this time step; similarly, $E_W(t)$ and $E_L(t)$ are the energy of the wind turbine and consumed by the load, respectively. In the calculation, it is considered $E(t) = P(t) \cdot \Delta t$, where $P(t)$ is the average power in the interval $(t-1, t)$.

When the battery is discharged:

$$C_{bat}(t) = C_{bat}(t-1)(1-\sigma) - \left(\frac{E_L(t)}{\eta_{inv}} - [E_{PV}(t) + E_W(t)] \right), \quad (2.4)$$

at the same time, the condition is fulfilled: $C_{batmin} \leq C_{bat}(t) \leq C_{batmax}$. Here, σ is an indicator characterizing self-discharge of batteries.

The level of consumption can be arbitrary. As a rule, it is some deterministic (traditional) function of time plus random fluctuations having a probability distribution close to normal. Since the combined power system is formed for a specific consumer, the nature of the load is predetermined or estimated retrospectively according to statistical data, and should be described in terms similar to the power system model.

2.2 Analysis of existing electrical energy storage systems and assessment of their effectiveness in traction power supply systems

Due to the active development of distributed generation systems in the traction power supply system and the peculiarities of its operation, there is a significant need for the development of storage systems. This problem is especially relevant for railway transport, since the train schedule, and therefore the load on the network, is strictly regulated. Analysis of the effectiveness of the application of the specified energy storage systems allows to determine their field of use. Today, there are 2 types of energy storage systems that are most common, named after the location. Depending on where they are installed, there are both mobile (so-called on-board) and stationary (so-called roadside) storage systems. The former are mostly located on the roof of each train or in the driver's cab, while the others are located at specific locations along the railway track.

On-board storage systems (OSS). Thanks to the application of the **OSS**, a significant amount of energy savings is ensured in the rolling stock, since the energy accumulated during the braking process can be used to power the same vehicle during acceleration. Due to the absence of linear losses, the efficiency of such storage systems is higher than those located along the road. The main advantages of using **OSS** relate to the possibility of minimizing power peaks during acceleration of vehicles, stabilizing the supply voltage and increasing the autonomy of the supply in the case of contactless operation [123], [124]. There are also known disadvantages of using such systems, namely: significant overall dimensions and weight, which leads to an increase in traction energy consumption by up to 2%. That is why **OSS** is preferred when designing new vehicles, rather than when modernizing existing rolling stock [123], [125]. Based on the experience of operating such systems, it should be noted that supercapacitor systems have become widespread, and when there is a need to ensure a significant degree of autonomy, the best option is the use of high-capacity lithium-ion and NiMH batteries. As for the use of flywheels in the construction of the **OSS**, due to certain limitations related to safety and cost, such a solution did not spread.

Roadside storage systems (RWS). If storage systems are located on the side of the road, braking energy comes to them from any nearby train and allows to provide electric energy to the consumer who needs it. Compared to **OSS**, there are no restrictions on their location and dimensional restrictions, but there are significantly higher losses in the power transmission line, which requires some attention. The advantage of such systems is the ability to minimize problems associated with voltage drops [126], [127]. The design of such systems is also, in the vast majority of cases, built using supercapacitors, lithium-ion and nickel-metal hydride batteries of significant capacity. Flywheels are more commonly used in stationary systems, as they can be placed in containers or underground [123].

The first regulatory document in this area is the IEC standard, namely IEC 62924:2017, which defines the requirements and test methods for a stationary storage system that will be used in a DC system to store energy and, if necessary, return it to the grid [128]. The standard clearly defines that the established requirements do not apply to on-board storage systems.

An option for implementing energy storage systems is the use of various local storage systems, namely: batteries, supercapacitors, flywheels, fuel cells, superconducting energy storage systems or their combinations [53]. Accumulators (most often lead-acid, nickel-metal hydride (Ni-MH) or Lithium-ION (Li-ION)), supercapacitors (EDLC (electrochemical) double-layer capacitors or ultracapacitors)

and flywheels (electromechanical ESSs). The factors that determine the best choice of technology relate mainly to energy capacity, charge/discharge rate and life cycle [126], [129]. In the case of using storage systems in a direct current network, it is recommended to use a DC/DC converter together with supercapacitors to fully utilize their significant voltage pulse, to reduce charge/discharge current peaks, and also to ensure charge state control over time [130]. In order to evaluate the efficiency of the specified systems, it is necessary to perform an analysis of the existing means of electric energy storage, to highlight their field of use and prospects for development.

Flywheels

Flywheels work by converting electrical energy into kinetic energy from a rotating mass and vice versa. The inertial energy store contains a body of rotation with a significant moment of inertia — the flywheel. The amount of stored kinetic energy depends on the speed of the rotating mass and inertia: the higher the speed and mass of the flywheel, the more rotational energy it can store. In general, a flywheel energy storage system (FESS) contains four key components: a rotor, a rotor bearing, an electric machine, and a power electronics interface [131]. The schematic diagram of FESS is presented in fig. 2.2. [132].

Fig. 2.2 Schematic diagram of FESS (Source [132])

FESS converts electrical energy into kinetic energy and stores mechanical energy in a high-speed rotor, which is connected to the electric machine through a bearing; then the kinetic energy is converted to electrical energy when needed. When the energy storage unit is charging, the flywheel rotates to a high speed (less than 10,000 revolutions per minute (rpm) for low speed and between 10,000 and 100,000 rpm for high speed) [133]. The FESS rotor is mounted in a vacuum chamber or a very low pressure chamber to eliminate or minimize frictional losses, also the performance of the flywheel is significantly affected by the geometry of the rotor [134], [135] and the tensile strength of the material, since the centrifugal force is proportional to the

square of the rotational speed [136]. The use of composite materials with high tensile strength allows FESS to achieve significant rotation speeds [137].

Modern high-speed FESSs cannot use conventional mechanical bearings due to the high friction generated, resulting in significant energy losses [138]. As a result, mechanical bearings require lubrication to minimize friction, and periodic maintenance is inevitable [139]. In addition, magnetic bearings are almost frictionless due to the benefits of magnetic levitation. In general, magnetic bearings can be divided into two categories, namely active magnetic bearings (AMB) and passive magnetic bearings (PMB). AMBs have high controllability, but the main drawback is power loss due to bias current [140]. In contrast, PMBs are based on the use of permanent magnets, which means that no input power is required. However, the construction of PMB is usually very complicated due to the limitations of Earnshaw's theorem [141].

The electric machine can operate as a motor when the FESS is charging or operate as a generator when the FESS is discharging. There are different types of electric machines accepted in FESSes. In general, electric machines can be divided into two categories: synchronous and asynchronous. The permanent magnet synchronous machine (PMSM) is one of the most popular synchronous machines, which has been widely used in FESS due to its high overall efficiency. Since the PMSM rotor flux is generated by a permanent magnet, the rotor losses are quite low [131]. High cost and low tensile strength of the material are the main disadvantages of PMSM. Compared to asynchronous machines (AMs), PMSMs are more sensitive to temperature, since their own coercive force decreases with increasing temperature [138]. As a typical type of induction machine, IMs are widely used in high-power applications due to their advantages in terms of torque, strength, construction, and cost. However, the design of the IM rotor is more complicated, as the rotor requires wires and brush connectors. In addition, rate limitation is another disadvantage of IM for high-speed FESS applications [142].

Power electronics also play a significant role in energy conversion. A power electronic device provides the appropriate voltage and current for other equipment [143]. Various topologies of power converters have been used for FESS, such as DC-AC converters, AC-AC converters, AC/DC-AC converters, and various combinations thereof [144].

The first stationary energy storage on an electrified railway using a flywheel was introduced in 1988 in Japan. The stationary storage was installed at the Zushi substation by Keihin Electric Express Railway. The device could convert the recuperation energy into mechanical energy using a generator engine and converter and back into electrical energy. The total power of the system was 2 MW and could

accumulate up to 25 kWh of energy, which allowed to save energy at the level of about 12% [145].

Electric Double Layer Capacitors (EDLC)

Unlike conventional capacitors, EDLC electrodes are permeated with an electrolyte, and the capacity is formed by the accumulated electrostatic charge at the interface between the electrode and the electrolyte [146], as shown in the schematic diagram in Fig. 2.3

From the given figure, we can conclude that double-layer capacitors are a hybrid of a capacitor and an electrochemical battery. The technical implementation of EDLC consists of an elementary cell with two electrodes made of nanoporous carbon materials and a liquid electrolyte, which ensures their isolation with a porous polymer or asbestos separator. This structure actually creates two series-connected supercapacitors: one of the plates, corresponding to the electric layer formed in the liquid, is virtual from a technical point of view, and the current is collected from the electric layers formed in the porous electrode; a metal/electrolyte interface several nanometers or even fractions of a nanometer thick is a dielectric. The reverse polarity of the plates in the system of two supercapacitors is formed due to the ion-conducting separator.

Fig. 2.3 Schematic diagram of EDLC. (Source [132])

When the EDLC operates in the charging phase, electrons move from the positive electrode to the negative electrode through the load circuit; this causes the cations and anions in the electrolyte to collect on the negative and positive electrodes, respectively. In the discharge phase, electrons move from the negative electrode to the positive electrode through the load circuit, and anions and cations begin to mix again [147]. Generally, EDLC electrodes are usually made of carbon-based materials

because of their high availability and low relative cost. Among the various types of carbon-based materials used in EDLC, activated carbon is the most widely used. In addition to the low cost, activated carbon materials also have the advantage of a high specific surface area (1000–2000 m²/g) [148]. The activation process can be achieved by a physical or chemical approach at high temperature or by mixing chemicals, respectively. However, due to poor pore size control during the activation process, it is difficult to optimize the pore size distribution in activated carbon materials [148]. Carbide-derived carbon (CDC) is another carbon-based material used in EDLCs because the pore size of CDCs can be properly optimized. Generally, CDC-based EDLCs have higher capacitance because the capacitance is determined by the CDC structure. As a single layer of carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb crystal lattice, graphene has received much attention in recent years. Graphene-based EDLCs can offer high performance due to their advantages related to long-cycle capability, flexibility, electrical characteristics, conductivity and excellent thermal stability [149].

Electrochemical energy storage

As one of the most commonly used energy storage devices, batteries store electrical energy in the form of chemical energy. Typically, a battery contains three key components: an anode, a cathode, and an electrolyte. Depending on the chemical material used in the electrodes, there is a wide range of batteries. In this section, a variety of storage batteries (BESS) are presented, such as lead-acid batteries, nickel batteries, sodium batteries, lithium-ion batteries, and redox batteries.

The principle of operation of an electrochemical energy storage device is based on the conversion of electrical energy into chemical energy during charging and, conversely, from chemical energy into electrical energy during discharge due to a reversible electrochemical reaction. Electrochemical energy storage is usually classified into primary batteries, secondary batteries, and fuel cells. Primary and secondary batteries use built-in chemical components, while chemically bound fuel energy is supplied externally for fuel cells. Primary batteries, unlike secondary batteries, cannot be recharged and cannot be called a true energy store. Depending on the chemical material used in the electrodes, there is a wide range of secondary electrochemical batteries.

Lead-acid batteries. The lead-acid battery was invented in 1859, so it is known as the oldest type of storage battery. Due to its low cost, high reliability and technological maturity, it has been widely used in economically sensitive applications. A typical lead-acid battery contains two electrodes: an anode made of spongy lead and a cathode made of lead dioxide. The two electrodes are separated by a separator, which is usually made of a microporous membrane or absorbent glass to prevent short

circuits. The electrodes and the separator are immersed in a dilute electrolyte based on sulfuric acid. In the discharge phase, the anode and cathode react with the electrolyte, forming lead sulfate and electrical energy. In contrast, lead sulfate and water react under the influence of external electrical energy to form lead and lead oxide. Thus, the number and size of sulfate crystals increase if the lead-acid battery is overdischarged or kept in a very low state of charge (SOC), which makes it very difficult for the sulfate crystals to split during charging, and may even cause a short circuit [150]. Compared to other types of batteries, lead-acid batteries have low energy density and limited cycle capacity [151]. To overcome these problems, various lead-acid batteries have been developed, such as valve-regulated lead-acid batteries, deep-cycle lead-acid batteries, and advanced lead-acid batteries [152]. Another disadvantage of lead-acid batteries is the use of toxic lead material in them, which causes metal pollution of the surrounding agricultural ecosystems during the production process. and at the disposal stage [153].

Often, to control the degree of discharge of lead-acid batteries, charging and recharging devices (CRD) are used, which perform the function of an energy source and the batteries are connected only in case of complete blackout. Due to the noted feature of lead-acid batteries and the inadmissibility of discharging them to 30% of the nominal capacity, there is a need to increase the installed capacity almost threefold to ensure the established requirements for the reliability of power supply. In the process of operation, it is necessary to periodically discharge the BESS (to preserve the operational indicators), as well as to carry out a constant review and control of the operating parameters. The listed disadvantages make BESS the most valuable element in an autonomous power supply system.

Nickel-based batteries. The nickel-cadmium (Ni-Cd) battery was invented in 1899 and enjoyed a high market share as a result of continuous performance improvements until the appearance of nickel-metal hydride (Ni-MH) and lithium-ion batteries [154]. The positive and negative electrodes of a typical Ni-Cd battery are made of nickel hydroxide and cadmium, respectively, and the electrolyte is made of alkaline potassium hydroxide. Ni-Cd batteries have low internal resistance and excellent ability to withstand high charge and discharge rates. In addition, Ni-Cd batteries can work in fast charging mode, since endothermic reactions occur during charging. Compared to other rechargeable batteries, another advantage of nickel-cadmium batteries is a wider operating temperature window. However, the "memory effect" and high self-discharge rate are the main bottlenecks of Ni-Cd batteries [155]. In addition, the cell voltage of Ni-Cd batteries is much lower than that of lead-acid and lithium-ion batteries, which means that more cells need to be connected in series

to achieve a certain voltage level. Each cell can have a different rate of self-discharge, which makes it difficult to balance the battery. From the point of view of health and environmental protection, nickel-cadmium batteries may pose a danger to the environment due to the use of toxic heavy materials such as cadmium. To overcome the disadvantages of nickel-cadmium batteries, nickel-metal hydride batteries have been developed, which offer better performance in terms of energy density and cycle capacity. The negative electrodes of Ni-MH batteries are made of a hydride alloy, so Ni-MH batteries are more environmentally friendly than Ni-Cd batteries. In addition, the influence of the "memory effect" is significantly reduced. High self-discharge rate is the main disadvantage of Ni-MH batteries. Although this weakness can be mitigated by using a functional separator, it significantly increases the cost and complexity of production [156].

Batteries based on sodium. Sodium batteries work due to the movement of sodium ions between the positive and negative electrodes. As a rule, the negative electrodes of sodium batteries are made of molten sodium. Different derivatives of sodium batteries have been developed using different materials in the positive electrodes and electrolytes. Among the candidates, the most common elements are sodium sulfur (NaS) and nickel chloride (NaNiCl₂) batteries. The positive electrode and electrolyte of the NaS battery are made of molten sulfur and solid beta-alumina ceramics, respectively. NaS batteries have high energy and power density, almost no self-discharge, excellent cycleability, and low cost. However, the main disadvantage of NaS batteries is the high requirement for operating temperature, usually in the range of 300–350 °C [157]. The sodium nickel chloride battery is also known as the ZEBRA battery and was developed in the mid-1980s. ZEBRA batteries have a higher cell voltage and better safety characteristics [158], but have a lower energy density than NaS batteries [159]. As a member of the fused cell family, ZEBRA batteries also require a high operating temperature, typically in the range of 270–350 °C [133]. Various room temperature sodium batteries have also been proposed to overcome the limitations of high operating temperature requirements [160]. However, research in this field is still in its infancy, and there is still a long way to go before its commercial application.

Lithium-ion batteries. The market share of lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries has grown rapidly in recent years due to their widespread use in small electronic devices and electric vehicles [154]. The mechanism of operation of Li-ion batteries is based on the movement of lithium ions. Lithium ions migrate from the positive electrode to the negative electrode during the charging process and return back during the discharging process. Compared to lead-acid and nickel batteries, lithium-ion batteries

have higher cell voltage, higher energy density, higher charge efficiency, and longer service life. Depending on the chemical materials used in the electrodes, various lithium-ion batteries have been developed:

- low-capacity batteries (tens to thousands of mAh), including lithium-cobalt-oxide (LCO), lithium-manganese oxide (LMO), lithium-nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide (NMC);

- batteries of significant capacity (from 10 to 250 A*h) lithium-nickel-cobalt-aluminum oxide (NCA), lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP), lithium-manganese (LNO) and lithium-titanate (LTO) batteries [161].

The main characteristics of these batteries are given in tables 2.1 and 2.2. LFP batteries and LMO batteries are highly regarded for their excellent performance in terms of power density. The discharge voltage curve of LFP batteries is quite flat, which allows LFP batteries to provide more stable output power with a certain discharge current at different SOC's [162].

Table 2.1 Comparative characteristics of lithium ion batteries of small capacity (Source: [163])

Features	Types of rechargeable batteries				
	LiSOCl ₂	LiSO ₂	LiNiO ₂	LiCoO ₂	LiNiMnCoO ₂
Specific energy capacity (W*h/kg)	650	270	200..250	150..240	150..240
Battery capacity, mAh	400..36000	500..33000	2600	6800	4000
Number of charge-discharge cycles	500..1000	450..1000	3..10	500..1000	1000..2000
Charge time, h	3	3	3	3	3
Self-discharge at room temperature, %	Less than 1% for the year	1..3	1..3	1,6	1..3
Voltage on the element, V	3,6	2,8..3	3,7	3,6	3,6..3,7
Load current relative to capacitance (C):					
-peak	20C	5C	5C	1C	2C
- the most acceptable	1C	до 0,5C	0,2C	до 0,8C	(0,7...1)C

Service temperature range, °C	-55..+85	-60..+70	-20..+60	-20..+60	0..+60
Peculiarities	need to be depassivized	minimum level of passivation	low internal resistance – less than 100 mΩ	poorly tolerate temperature reduction, short service life, significant cost	significant current output, can be charged at negative temperatures, full discharge contributes to thermal breakdown

In addition, LFP batteries also have higher safety and relatively longer lifetime [164]. However, the main disadvantage of LFP batteries is the relatively low specific energy value. Compared to other Li-ion batteries, which have a nominal voltage of about 3.6V to 3.7V, the nominal voltage of LFP batteries is only 3.2V. Another disadvantage of LFP batteries is their relatively high self-discharge rate compared to other batteries, although the self-discharge rate of LFP batteries is much lower than that of lead-acid and nickel batteries. In contrast, LMO batteries allow obtaining specific energy and a lower self-discharge rate than LFP batteries, but their cycling capacity is low.

Table 2.2 Comparative characteristics of large capacity lithium ion batteries (Source: [163])

Features	Types of rechargeable batteries					
	LiFePO ₄	LiNiCoAlO ₂	LiMnO ₂ LiMn ₂ O ₄	LiCoMnNi O ₂	Li ₄ Ti ₅ O ₁₂	Lithium Polymer Compounds
Specific energy capacity (W*h/kg)	90..140	200..260	150..260	150..260	65..80	150..180
Battery capacity, A*h	до 200	2,5..15	33	10..200	15..120	3..200
Number of charge-discharge cycles	1500..7000	500..1000	300..700	1000..10000	3000..16000	1000..10000
Charge time, h	1..2	3	3	1	0,5..3	1..3
Self-discharge at room temperature, %	1%	2..4	2	1	1	1..5

Voltage on the element, V	3,6..4	3,6	3,7	3,7..3,8	2,4	3,7
Load current relative to capacitance (C):						
-peak						
- the most acceptable	до 25C 1C	2C 1C	3C (0,7...1)C	3C (2...3)C	до 10C (0,5...1)C	(3..5)C 2C
Service temperature range	-10..+60	-20..+60	-40..+70	-30..+50	-40..+80	0..+60
Peculiarities	the safest lithium batteries that can produce significant discharge currents	significant capacitance, resistant to mechanical influences, explosive	significant power, insignificant capacity, safer compared to LiCo	low internal resistance (< 30 mΩ)	one of the safest lithium batteries, characterized by rapid discharge at low temperature	small weight, low internal resistance (< 0.5...1.2 mΩ), high reliability

To overcome this problem, LMO batteries are usually used in combination with NMC batteries to increase their capacity value and cycling ability. NMC and NCA batteries are typical nickel-based lithium-ion batteries. Compared to LFP and LMO batteries, NMC and NCA batteries have a higher capacity, but their cost increases due to the use of cobalt material. Compared to LFP batteries, NMC and NCA have problems with cycling and relative stability [164]. While LTOs have emerged as a promising type of Li-ion batteries due to their high capacity and extremely long cycle life [165]. However, the main disadvantages of LTO batteries are relatively low specific energy and high cost [166].

The most affordable in terms of cost are lithium-manganese dioxide and lithium-sulphur dioxide batteries. The first are characterized by a small self-discharge current (2..2.5% per year) and a significant storage period (more than 10 years), as well as a wide range of operating temperatures (-40...+85° C). The operating voltage at the output of such a battery is characterized by rather low stability: in the discharge range from 0 to 60%, the operating voltage decreases from 3.0 to 2.5 V, and with a greater discharge, it generally decreases to 1.7 V.

Lithium-dioxide-sulfur batteries have a low self-discharge current (1..2% per year) and maintain performance in the operating temperature range from -55 to +70° C. It has a fairly stable output voltage characteristic, which remains at the level of 2.6...2.9 V when discharged to 85%, and then sharply drops to 2 V. Disadvantages of this type of battery include high internal pressure and the danger of intense heating.

Lithium-thionyl chloride batteries have the highest specific energy density and the lowest self-discharge current (less than 1% per year). In addition, such batteries have the best voltage stability during discharge: the voltage remains at the level of 3.6 V at the degree of discharge up to 85%, and only then sharply decreases to 3.1 V.

In recent years, the distribution by types of lithium batteries is as follows: NMC – 29%, NCA – 10%, LFP – 22%, LCO – 25%, LMO – 13%, LTO – 1%. There is a forecast that the share of NMC and NCA will increase to 58% by 2025.

The use of lithium-ion batteries with a gel electrolyte allows you to eliminate the control of the level, temperature and density of the electrolyte, which reduces maintenance costs. In addition, they have a rather significant period of use - from 10 to 15 years. Taking into account the noted advantages of lithium-ion batteries, batteries listed in table 2.1 can be used for power supply, and for more powerful installations - in table 2.2.

One of the first successful cases of using storage systems based on lithium-ion batteries manufactured by Hitachi was their installation at the Myodani substation of the Seishin-Yamate line of the Kobe city subway in 2004. The nominal power of the system was 1 MW, and the nominal energy was 37.4 kWh, which made it possible to save more than 10% of the annual electricity consumption.

Redox batteries. A redox battery (RFB) is an electrochemical energy storage device that provides electrical energy using two active materials in liquid form. Two active substances are usually separated by an ion exchange membrane; reduction and oxidation reactions occur on both sides of the ion exchange membrane during fluid pumping. All-vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs), polysulfide bromine flow batteries (PSFBs), and zinc bromine flow batteries (ZBFBs) are the most common and commercially available flow batteries. Compared to other types of batteries, the main advantages of RFBs are their excellent scalability, long service life, and independent determination of energy and power size [167]. In addition, since RFB electrolytes are stored in separate reservoirs, RFBs hardly cause self-discharge phenomena. Thanks to the special design, the temperature of the cell can be easily adjusted by adjusting the electrolyte flow. However, inappropriate operating temperature causes the problem of precipitation, which reduces the performance of RFB and accelerates degradation. Therefore, the operating temperature of RFB is usually limited to 15–35 °C [168]. In

addition, although RFB-based ESSs have been used at the grid level, RFBs still face major challenges for their use in transportation applications due to their low energy density and power density [169].

Comparison of energy storage types

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) and nickel-metal hydride (Ni-MH) batteries are the most common types of batteries used in vehicles [170], so the comparison will be made for them. Comparative characteristics of the considered types of energy storage are given in table 2.3.

Table 2.3 Comparative characteristics of storage types (Source: [132])

	Flywheel	EDLC	Li-ion	Ni-MH
Power rating (MW)	0.25–20	0–0.3	0–100	0.001–0.03
Energy rating (MWh)	0.0052–5	0.0005	0.004–10	0.01–0.05
Cycle efficiency (%)	90–95	84–97	75–97	65–70
Daily self-discharge (%)	>20% per hour	–20–30	0.1–0.3	1–2
Typical storage duration	seconds–minutes	seconds–hours	minutes–days	minutes–days
Response time	Seconds	Milliseconds	Milliseconds	Milliseconds
Lifetime (years)	15–20	10–30	8–15	15–20
Life cycles (cycles)	20,000–100,000	>100,000	1000–10,000	1500–3000
Power capital cost (\$/kW)	250–350	100–300	900–1300	420–1200
Energy capital cost (\$/kWh)	1000–5000	300–2000	273–1000	240–1200

Since stationary SEs are meant, when comparing the considered technologies, such indicators as gravimetric and volumetric energy density and not taken into account power density are taken into account. Energy storage for stationary railways can be divided into two categories: short-term and long-term, depending on the duration of storage.

The short-duration category (flywheels and electric double-layer capacitors) usually has a small energy rating and is used in high-power systems—operating period adjustable to seconds or minutes—high life cycles and lifetimes, and high lifetime efficiency. Short-term energy storage is more suitable for high power applications due to lower capital costs per unit of power. The long-duration category (electrochemical batteries) can store energy for hours or even days.

Long-term energy storage is more suitable for high energy applications due to relatively low capital costs per unit of energy. However, the capital costs and capital cost of energy for lithium-ion batteries are practically comparable, which is a fair explanation for the current wide range of development and application of lithium-ion batteries. In addition, the fast response time ensures successful application in both long-term and short-term categories. Figure 2.4 shows the application areas of

different storage methods in stationary systems used on electrified railways, according to stored energy and output power.

Figure 2.4 Power rating and energy capacity of different stationary (wayside) ESSs for electrified railway systems (Source: [132]).

As can be seen in Figure 2, EDLCs and flywheels are used for high-power, low-power applications, while batteries have proven successful in both short-term and long-term applications. Stationary energy storage can recover and release energy produced by multiple trains on a line as soon as it is needed [166]. Energy savings can be up to 45% [167].

Supercapacitors are the most cost-effective with a service life of 10 years. In [167], the optimal configuration for the use of roadside energy storage in direct current electric railway transport systems is defined in the conditions of maximum regenerative energy saving from trains and minimal capital and operating costs for storage technology.

2.3 Energy recovery in the railway power supply system

Another direction in the development of energy storage systems is the ability of the vast majority of modern traction vehicles for regenerative braking. The use of regenerative braking energy is a rather short-term phenomenon. Asynchronous motors of railway transport act as generators when braking, converting kinetic energy into electrical energy. Traction trains and power supply devices in the same power section use most of the regenerative braking energy, and the rest is returned to the power grid [165]. The energy obtained as a result of this process can be used by another vehicle that is in the vicinity of the braking rolling stock. If the receiving vehicle cannot receive all the energy, then it is lost to the braking resistors to keep the network voltage

at the appropriate level. The maximum power of recovery energy varies within fairly wide limits from 1.5 MW (metro, tram) to 6 MW in the case of railway applications [171]. Damping of voltage fluctuations is a rather short-term process. The appearance of excess energy during braking of railway transport increases the voltage in the network. Overvoltage can damage electronic equipment, traction and compressor motors located in trains and insulators. It can also lead to malfunction and failure of protection and relays [172]. When the power supply is insufficient to meet the traction load requirements, the voltage drops significantly. The minimum allowable voltage drop or reduction in railway electrical networks is 33% [173]. Instability of voltage in the network not only creates various risks for the power system, but can lead to the failure of the power system [162]. ESSs installed as a stationary system at weak points of the line are expected to reduce line voltage fluctuations. Practical examples of the use of energy storage to reduce the voltage drop during network load are shown in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4 Examples of EES using for voltage regulation Source: [132]

Li-ion Battery			EDLC (Supercapacitor)			Flywheel		
P, kW	W, kWh	Effects	P, kW	W, kWh	Effects	P, kW	W, kWh	Effects
2000	500	reduces voltage drop by 5.26%	1865.6	10.386	reduces voltage drop by 13%	300	3	reduces voltage drop by 12.7%

Recovery in various electric transport systems makes it possible to reduce energy consumption by 30–50%, but in the current traction power supply systems, the recovery factor does not exceed 5–10% [174]. The main disadvantage of this measure is the complication and increase in the cost of rolling stock equipment and increased wear of the generator. It should be noted several well-known factors that prevent the full use of the potential of this phenomenon, namely:

- the occurrence of excess recovery energy values due to the absence of trains on the line in traction mode,
- relative instability of recovery energy.

The noted problems can be solved by the following measures [132]:

- synchronize the load in the electric traction system;
- ensure the transfer of recovery energy to the external network; and
- save energy through the use of autonomous energy storage systems.

The use of recovery energy by other means of rolling stock allows to increase the energy efficiency of the system, and also reduces the level of peak consumption from the external system. The optimization of the traffic schedule on railways [175] and the implementation of the management strategy [145] are actively used to ensure the specified measure, however, the schedule and operating characteristics of railway

transport have certain limitations associated with the peculiarities of the transport market and the effect of safety rules.

The next option for recuperative energy storage is the use of an external network (for example, an external AC network) through substations. In AC traction power supply systems, inverters are installed on rolling stock to transfer excess recovery energy. Therefore, the return of energy to the primary power supply system has a number of significant disadvantages:

- 1) the construction of the traction substation is complicated;
- 2) when the inverter is turned on, circulating currents occur in the circuit with rectifiers, accordingly, the energy transmitted to the primary network is of low quality;
- 3) the power mode of non-traction consumers deteriorates;
- 4) the tension in the traction network increases significantly.

For direct current railway lines, this approach is implemented based on equipping traction substations with direct current inverters, which allow current to flow in two directions [45]. Such traction substations are called reversible, bidirectional, inverting or active. The application of this method allows you to transfer significant amounts of energy to the external alternating current network and ensures almost full use of braking energy, with the exception of internal losses during its transmission to the network. A number of publications [176], [177], [178] are devoted to the issue of the design development of reversible substations. The well-known design of the hybrid system of direct current traction power supply, which combines a photoelectric and reversible converter, significantly reduces energy consumption from the network, increases the reliability and quality of electricity. The DC/DC converter in the photovoltaic system provides a voltage increase and controls the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) [179], [180], [181], which allows reducing the voltage deviation due to the control of the filling factor of the load schedule. In the case of using such a system in a network of low and medium power, a two-level topology of the voltage source is effective, in the case of use in a network of significant power, a multi-module topology should be used to increase the bandwidth and reduce the influence of higher harmonics [182]. The disadvantage of such systems is the deterioration of the operating mode of the traction power supply system, due to the generation of higher harmonics from the traction systems to the external network [78].

Reversible traction substations.

The concept of a DC reversing substation arose from the need to improve the receptivity of a power line so that braking energy can be transferred to a greater extent. It is also necessary to ensure the appropriate level of electrical energy quality indicators from the power source. The regenerative braking energy is sent to the AC

network for consumption by other electrical equipment at the substation or even to the general network [126]. The main functions that a reversible substation should perform are [158]

- leave the priority of the natural exchange of recuperation energy between vehicles;
- to minimize the level of harmonics, ensuring the quality of electrical energy from both alternating and direct current;
- maintain the output voltage at the appropriate level in various modes;
- in order to ensure the possibility of reverse flow of electricity at a conventional DC traction substation equipped with an uncontrolled rectifier, the inverter must be connected anti-parallel to the rectifier. Thus, the existing group consisting of a traction transformer and a diode rectifier is preserved, and the possibility of energy recovery is achieved with minimal interference in the operating circuit. Depending on the type of inverter selected, a static converter providing bidirectional energy flow may consist of [126], [183];
 - diode rectifier and thyristor inverter, also known as thyristor switching inverter (TSI);
 - diode rectifier and PWM inverter based on fully controlled keys.

In the event that the system can be upgraded, the uncontrolled pull-up rectifier can be replaced, for example, with a reversible thyristor rectifier [183], an IGBT-based thyristor bridge rectifier [184]. Accordingly, the need to replace the existing transformer makes this solution more complex and expensive. Obviously, in new DC traction substations, a high-performance bidirectional converter can be considered from the outset. The different approaches to implementing reversible DC traction substations, including the main systems available on the market, are summarized below.

- Reversible substations with diode rectifier and thyristor inverter;
- Reversible substations with diode rectifier and PWM inverter;
- Reversible substations with reversible thyristor rectifiers;
- Reversible substations with thyristor rectifier and PWM inverter.

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the most universal energy recovery systems are on-board storage systems on rolling stock and storage systems at traction substations, which requires further research to improve the efficiency of such systems. In the future, the development of new technologies to achieve high-performance storage equipment (high energy capacity, very good charge/discharge rate and small size) at competitive prices may restore braking energy storage solutions in both on-board and stationary equipment. At the same time, the direction of

improvement can be the introduction of global algorithms for energy optimization of traction systems based on new hardware structures with high reliability and acceptable cost.

2.4 Increasing the efficiency of energy storage systems

The electrical energy storage may be installed in a traction substation or in a sectional cab as shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5. Places of incorporation of the energy storage into the electric traction power supply system (Source: Own study)

The primary function of the energy storage, regardless of the workplace, is to stabilize the voltage in the overhead contact line at the assumed level. In the case of energy storage installed in a traction substation, it limits the peak values of the power drawn from the power system. In addition, warehouses collect regenerative braking energy, which they later transfer to the overhead contact line during increased load.

It is important that the warehouse can stabilize the voltage in the overhead contact line only when there is energy stored in it and the current drawn from the warehouse is sufficient to stabilize the voltage.

The warehouse is controlled by entering 4 voltage values on the control panel of the converter. The voltage values U_{c1} and U_{c2} determine the transition to charging mode. The charging mode starts when the voltage at the warehouse input from the overhead contact line reaches the value U_{c2} . The charging current is selected by the warehouse control system so that the voltage in the network does not fall below the U_{c2} value. The maximum charge current value is simultaneously determined by the battery BMS. The charging mode continues until the voltage in the overhead contact line (at the warehouse input) falls below the level specified as U_{c1} . U_{c1} is lower than U_{c2} , which prevents the charging function from being deactivated in the event of voltage fluctuations in the overhead contact line.

The discharge mode of the energy storage starts when the input voltage from the overhead contact line side falls below the value of U_{d1} . This also means that the

unloading of the warehouse will be carried out in the absence of voltage in the overhead contact line. The storage current is selected automatically so that the voltage does not fall below U_{d1} . The voltage U_{d1} can be stabilized for a load current range not exceeding the maximum discharge current specified by the BMS. The warehouse operates in the discharge mode until the batteries are discharged (voltage drop on the cells referred to as the minimum) or until the voltage at the input of the warehouse rises to the value of U_{d2} .

Switching on the warehouse operating modes is shown graphically in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6. Modes of energy storage (charging / discharging) depending on the voltage level at the storage device inputs at the contact line side (Source: own study based on [7], [9])

The value of the maximum charging and discharging current of the batteries, and thus the value of the current drawn or returned by the energy storage, is determined by the voltage on the battery cells. This voltage is determined by measuring on each of the battery cells. Due to the care for the life of the batteries, the minimum and maximum voltage is respectively higher or lower than the permissible values. The BMS software analyzes the voltage values on the individual battery cells, calculates the maximum charging and discharging current, and then sends the information to the converter. Based on this data, the converter automatically sets the current flowing into or out of the warehouse and into the batteries.

If any of the battery cells reaches the assumed maximum voltage, the charging process is not implemented regardless of exceeding the U_{c2} voltage at the input of the storage. A similar behavior of the warehouse occurs with the occurrence of a minimum voltage on the battery cells. Then, a drop in the voltage at the output of the warehouse below the U_{d1} level will not trigger switching the warehouse into the discharge mode. The locking of the charging or discharging mode is communicated by the BMS and displayed on the inverter panel. It lasts until the voltage on the battery cells changes to a value between the minimum and maximum as a result of charging or discharging the storage.

Starting the energy storage. After installing and connecting all elements of the energy storage described in chapter 2, the insulation of the entire system was checked.

Then the inverter is switched on in the idle state and the battery automation and control systems are switched on. The correct communication between the BMS battery and the inverter has been checked. The accuracy of measurements made by control systems was also checked by measuring voltages at selected points of the system.

After synchronizing the batteries with the inverter, a controlled battery charging was carried out. For this purpose, the inverter program established a specific charging current value of initially 50 A, and then it was reduced as the battery charge reached its maximum level. The source of voltage was a rectifier unit equipped with the IK short-circuit laboratory.

Due to the high internal resistance of the rectifier unit resulting in significant changes in the output voltage of the unit, it was necessary to increase the idle voltage of the unit and the U_{c2} voltage several times, so that the voltage drop on the resistance of the rectifier unit does not cause the voltage drop at the warehouse input below U_{c1} , which results in switching off the warehouse charging mode.

Charging was carried out in several cycles, between which there was automatic balancing of batteries – balancing the voltage on individual cells.

CHAPTER 3 SELECTED PROBLEMS OF ELECTRICAL ENERGY SUPPLY IN AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS OF NON-TRACTION ELECTRICAL SUPPLY OF RAILWAYS

3.1 Provision of electrical energy for control systems

The characteristics of railway traffic control systems from the point of view of their energy needs can be shown using the following classification:

1) in terms of the type of equipment used on:

- signaling switching devices, traffic light switching devices,
- mechanical devices with form signaling, mechanical devices with light signaling,
- electromechanical devices,
- relay and hybrid devices,
- computer devices;

2) from the point of view of their location in the area:

- station devices - this group can also include semi-automatic blocking of lines, since their elements are located at stations or service stations, and therefore the power supply of these stations is used for their power supply,

- linear devices with separate automatic line blocking devices and devices used at level crossings of railway lines with carriageways,

- crossing control devices and turnouts, which have been allocated to a separate group due to their operation with both stationary and linear devices, and the use of

certain types of these systems often necessitates the introduction of additional power requirements.

However, in practice, mixed solutions are very common, in which standard circuits for one type of device are used for other types of devices. Examples include circuits that are typical of relay devices used in mechanical devices, such as the electrical control inputs of switches or the isolation of tracks and switches. At the same time, the rules for powering modified devices must also take into account the requirements of the introduced schemes. The division adopted above corresponds to the current prevailing concept of coverage and presentation of requirements for railway traffic management systems in the development of technical and operational standards for certain categories of railway lines.

Between large stations there are intermediate stations, junctions, stopping points, crossings, linear track buildings on the racetrack, as well as automatic blocking devices of SCB. These are consumers of auxiliary electricity, intended for the maintenance of interstation equipment, for example, the lighting load of intermediate stations, stopping points, linear and track buildings, etc. Their characteristic feature is significant branching along the tracks and relatively low power. The power supply system of non-traction consumers also has certain features, namely: significant branching due to the dispersion of the latter and characterized by relatively small electrical loads. The approximate capacity and level of electric energy consumption of the specified group of consumers are given in tables 3.1 and 3.2.

Table 3.1. Indicators of unit energy consumption for selected railway traffic control elements Source: [185]

Name of receiver EE	Power consumption [VA]
Switch with relay: induction electronic	70 40
Schemes of a switch with a motor: single-phase three-phase	1320 3x450
One lamp on the semaphore	45
Repeated beep: single double	170 310
Nominal power of the transformer (idle): 45 VA 109 VA 200 VA	30 75 100
Control scheme of the switching point drive in devices of the EI type	80
Computer power supplies	2x750
Automatic signaling of a railway crossing	500 ÷ 1500

Table 3.2 Average annual report on energy consumption Source: [185]

Name of the object	Annual energy consumption [kWh]	Average monthly consumption [kWh]	Average daily consumption [kWh]	Average hourly consumption [kW]
Self-locking station	5101	425,08	14,17	0,59
Rail crossing	5425	452,08	15,07	0,63
DSAT devices	7789	649,08	21,64	0,90

In order to provide electric energy to the specified consumers, two lines are laid in the area between the large stations: one – the overhead line of the Central Railway Station - designed to power the loads of the Central Railway Station and the second - the longitudinal power supply line (LPSL) – to provide electricity to the remaining consumers in the area. A part of these consumers (loading of SCB devices, communication, etc.) has the first category of ensuring the reliability of power supply and requires the presence of two independent sources of electrical energy. Consumers of the first category and a number of low-power consumers of the second category (SCB and communication loads, catenary sectioning posts, telemechanics controlled points, etc.) receive power from two lines. In some cases, reservation is made from power stations of the Central Railway Station with a diesel-generator unit (DG). It is also allowed to use a backup power supply from a 6, 10, 35 kV line of industrial use. PL SCB are intended only for powering signal points on races and electrical centralization (EC) posts at small stations. LPSL and "two wire-rail" (TWR), in addition to reserving the SCB, provide power to railway service and residential buildings, illumination of the territory of railway stations, electric tools for road works and other loads.

The main power scheme is one-sided (*console*) power supply of lines, which allows to ensure fairly high reliability and effective protection against multi-phase short circuits and selective protection against earth faults. With the OTL console scheme, the SCB receives power from one of the adjacent substations. In the event that the circuit breaker of the feeder substation is turned off and the voltage on the power line disappears, the power is automatically transferred to the adjacent substation.

With the counter-console scheme of the OTL SCB receives power from two adjacent substations with sectioning in the middle of the line. For sectioning of the line, sectioning points with a switch equipped with an Automatic inclusion of reserve (AIR) device are installed. The counter-cantilever power supply scheme has a number

of advantages: in the event of damage, only half of the line is disconnected and voltage and energy losses are reduced compared to the cantilever supply scheme. However, this scheme requires additional capital costs for the construction of sectioning points or backup power supply and can be recommended in areas where there are no longitudinal power supply lines from which the backup power supply of SCB loads is provided, and in case of long power arms, which are 40...50 km or more.

In the presence of backup power supply of SCB loads from the longitudinal power supply line and equipment of OTL SCB with automatic repeated inclusion (ARI) and AIR devices, the cantilever power supply scheme ensures a sufficiently reliable power supply of self-locking.

Longitudinal power supply lines of 6-10 kV on electrified direct current railways receive power from busbars of switchgears of 6-10 kV traction substations laid on catenary supports and single-circuit high-voltage alternating current lines with a nominal voltage of 10 kV. A typical scheme of such a distribution is shown in fig. 3.1.

In the electrified areas of alternating current, the three-phase system of longitudinal power supply from 27.5 kV buses, TWR which are connected to the traction windings of substation transformers, became widespread (Fig. 3.2).

Fig. 3.1 Implementation of the power supply system of self-locking devices in the direct current network (LPSL – longitudinal power supply line; OCS – overhead catenary system; PL SCB – power line signalling, centralization and blocking; DB – distribution board) (Source: [186])

Fig. 3.2 Implementation of the power system of self-locking devices in an alternating current network (TWR – two wire-rail; OCS – overhead catenary system; PL SCB – power line signalling, centralization and blocking; DB – distribution board) (Source: [186])

Two phases of this system are placed on catenary supports, and the third is connected to rails. At the same time, each of the additional wires of the TWR system is connected to different phases, from which the adjacent sections of the contact network, located on both sides of the neutral insert, will receive power.

The SCB and LPSL lines are divided into separate sections - power arms, each of which must be supplied with two-way power from special power points. Typical power supply schemes provide for the supply of overhead lines of the SCB with a voltage of 6 kV; 10 kV through a separate transformer. At the traction substations, power supply of the SCB lines is provided through a step-up transformer from the 0.4 kV buses, which in turn receive power from the substation's own demand transformers.

A feature of each KTP is a significant number of consumers of electricity: devices of the SCB, communication, track and locomotive management. All devices (SCB, communications, etc.) are connected to power sources by independent lines with installation on input channels or in relay cabinets of the equipment, which ensures automatic transition from the main power supply to the backup in case of voltage drop below the set level. When power is turned off from the main arm, a backup source from the other end of the arm is automatically connected.

The need to use transformers that perform the role of separating (separating) is due to the following considerations:

1. On lines opened by protection when the phase is shorted to the ground, as well as in the case when the short-circuit current to the ground does not exceed 5 A, reinforced concrete supports in uninhabited areas may not be grounded. In the case of connecting the SCB lines directly to the buses of the DB 6; In 10 kV substations,

the earth fault current can reach values greater than 5 A, and then these lines would have to be made in such a way that they open during an earth fault, or provide for the grounding of supports in uninhabited areas.

2. With the adopted schemes for connecting the SCB lines through isolating transformers, the maximum three-phase short-circuit current (SCC) reaches several tens of amperes, and the minimum two-phase SCC can reach 10 A. When connecting SCB lines directly to buses 6; 10 kV substations, SCC can significantly exceed 0.15 kA, so the fuses in this case must have a significant breaking capacity.

An example of a single-line electrical circuit of such an element is shown in Figure 3.3.

Fig. 3.3 Single-line power supply scheme for SCB lines (Source: [186])

One of the disadvantages of the TWR line is the voltage fluctuation caused by fluctuations on the 27.5 kV busbars of traction substations and changes in electrical force (EF) induced in the single-wire wire-rail circuit from the AC traction network. Calculations show that the maximum deviation of the voltage in the lines from the inductive influence of the traction network in normal mode is no more than $\pm 6\%$. In the forced mode (disconnection of one of the traction substations) and the cantilever power supply of the catenary network, the maximum deviation of the voltage on the 220 V side of the transformers is from 180 V to 240 V, or within the range of $-20\% \dots +10\%$.

In alternating current sections with 25 Hz self-locking rail circuits, frequency converters are used in circuits that provide voltage stabilization at the output of the converter. When the mains voltage changes from 190 V to 270 V, the output voltage of the converter changes by only 5 V (2.3% of the nominal).

The load of the SCB PL is determined by the total power of the auto-blocking devices and ECs connected to the line. The uniformity of the loading of the phases of the three-phase line by single-phase loads on the race is achieved by periodic transposition of the wires, the unevenness of the loading of the PL phases should not

exceed 10%, but in operating conditions, for various reasons, this requirement is not always met. A feature of EC stations is load asymmetry due to the presence of frequency converters connected to one phase.

3.2 Reliability of elements of the energy supply system for consumers on the example of railways of Ukraine

Incorrect functioning of SCB devices can occur due to the influence of traction current on rail circuits in normal and emergency modes of operation of the power supply system and as a result of a short-term interruption or decrease in the value of the supply voltage.

During races, interruptions in the power supply in the overhead lines of the Central Railway Station lead to the de-energization of traffic lights, the signal readings of which are restored after the supply of voltage. Therefore, in the devices of the SCB, a delay of up to 2...3 s is provided for the switching of all relays included in the circuit of signal relays, when the voltage drops for a time of up to 1.3 s. In some cases, an increase in the deceleration time up to 5...6 seconds is permitted. The causes failures are often unstable power supply of rail circuits, which arises both from fluctuating voltage in the power system and as a result of loss of contact on disconnectors. When the supply voltage is reduced to less than 210 V, failures are possible due to a decrease in the signal current at the end of a long rail chain, as well as a change in the suspension value of the receiving coils during movement. An increase in the voltage of more than 250 V leads to the blowing of fuses, the activation of protective machines, the melting of the windings of equipment that is under voltage of the network [187].

The reasons for the violation of the normal mode of operation of the overhead line of the Central Railway Station are: short circuits in the lines; the collision of an oversized vehicle, as well as intensive corrosion; shorting of wires in the case of a large overhang, broken insulators or broken wires. External influences can also include atmospheric overvoltages (6.1%), effects of traction currents of electrified direct and alternating current railways (9.2%).

Damage to cable inserts occurs mainly during earthworks, stretching of the cable during subsidence of the soil, ingress of moisture into the coupling or funnel, corrosion of the cable sheath.

The most frequent causes of short-circuits in the overhead line of the SCB are: lightning discharges, causing insulators to overlap, shorting of wires of different phases by birds, wires being crushed, branches of trees hitting the wires during strong winds, etc. Most of them are of a short-term nature, since the causes that caused them

are self-resolving, and the electric arc that arose at the place of the circuit is extinguished when the switch is turned off by the action of the relay protection.

The largest number of damaged in the PL SCB is due to single-phase short-circuits to the ground (about 50%) and two-phase **short-circuits** (about 30%), the latter can occur when two phases are closed directly or due to transient resistance at two short-circuits of different phases to the ground at different points of the PL SCB [188].

The total length of SCB lines is tens of thousands of kilometers, which leads to a significant amount of damage, especially single-phase earth faults (earth faults). This is primarily related to the process of insulation deterioration or tree branches touching the wires. Another negative factor on the number of occurrences of emergency situations is the influence of high voltage of the backup line (two conductors-rail, 27.5 kV) and the contact wire on the working line of the SCB. The induced voltage on the phases of the line significantly changes the value of the voltages of the phases of the working line in relation to the ground.

The feeders supplying the 6 (10) kV overhead line of the SCB are equipped with maximum current protection (MTP) and at minimum voltage on the supply buses, acting to turn off the switch. Protections for single-phase earth faults act either on the signal or, if high-voltage and low-voltage groundings on power transformers are combined, on the disconnection of the switch. To limit the currents of all types of short circuits on the feeders of the SCB, galvanic decoupling in the form of a double transformation (6/0.4 – 0.4/6 kV) is used [189].

Since the SCB overhead line is a line with an isolated neutral galvanically decoupled from the substation buses by a step-up transformer of 0.23/6(10) kV, single-phase shorting of any wire to the ground does not change the interphase voltages and does not affect the SCB cable networks. In the areas where overhead communication lines are used in SCB devices, laid along overhead lines of SCB, single-phase short-circuits break the symmetry of the electromagnetic system and lead to failures in SCB. There is also an increase in the voltage of the undamaged phases, which can quickly lead to the transition of the **earth faults** to a more dangerous type of accident.

Ground fault currents usually do not exceed units of amperes and are determined by the capacity of the wires. At a voltage of 6 kV, the single-phase short-circuit current is about 20 mA per 1 km of the transmission line, and at a voltage of 10 kV – 26 mA. The implementation of measures aimed at increasing emergency currents do not achieve the desired result. Therefore, overhead lines of the SCB are equipped with single-phase short-circuited monitoring devices intended for prompt notification of personnel about damage and taking measures to eliminate it. The permissible time of operation of a high-voltage line in the mode of a single-phase

circuit is up to two hours. However, it should be borne in mind that with a single-phase short-circuit, an arc may occur, which causes transient processes with the appearance of high-frequency harmonics, which create resonance in some elements of the circuit and insulation breakdown.

As a rule, high-voltage lines of **LPSL** do not have isolating transformers and are directly connected to the busbars of the substation. Consequently, the total capacity of the wires of all lines connected to the busbars of the source is relatively large, and the short-circuit current to the ground will be significant. Therefore, the protection in the event of a short circuit to the ground should act to turn off the switch of the damaged PE line. The tripping time of an emergency in a network with a phase voltage of up to 230 V should not exceed 0.4 s, and for a distribution network - 5 s.

The voltage on the open delta of the feeder voltage transformer indicates the appearance of a zero sequence. It occurs with asymmetry on the feeder for various reasons:

- from a single-phase circuit;
- that of induced voltage;
- uneven load of the phases on the transmission line, for example - in case of loss of contact on the disconnector.

SCB lines are equipped with devices for **AIR** and **ARI**. In accordance with the requirements, the complete cycle time of the switch disconnection during protection action, the subsequent reactivation at the main power supply point or **AIR** at the standby one should be 1.3 seconds, all KTP cameras are equipped with remote control (most of them are remote control), switches. When the duration of the maximum current protection is no more than 0.5 seconds. and the time of one-time reactivation is no more than 0.3-0.4 seconds. taking into account the own time of turning off and turning on the contactor or switch of the overhead line, the time of starting the **AIR** from the backup power point of the overhead line should not exceed 1.0-1.1 seconds.

To obtain different voltages with a zero isolated from the ground, isolating power transformers of the **TC** type are used at the power stations - single-phase or three-phase. Their characteristic feature is significant heating of the magnetic wire (more than 60 C). Thus, the idle current (**IC**) of the **TC-10** is 10% of the nominal value due to the insufficient number of turns of the primary winding.

Failures of fuses of the **IKH** type occur mainly when fuses burn out from short-circuits in the secondary circuit of OM transformers, intense corrosion of the working spiral when the sealing of the fuse is broken when it is heated due to poor contact or atmospheric overvoltages.

Damage to OM transformers occurs when moisture penetrates inside the housing, which leads to a breakdown of the high-voltage winding, as well as when mechanical destruction of high-voltage bushing insulators. In the event of a thunderstorm and an overvoltage in the power lines, the arresters do not operate simultaneously. There is a large potential difference between the phases, and part of the line manages to burn out at the site of the lightning discharge. ПКН fuses work only in the event of a short-circuit of the high-voltage winding in the immediate vicinity of the terminals.

With a large number of linear disconnectors in the overhead lines of the SCB, there are periodically cases of voltage drop in one of the phases due to contact failure, which also leads to failures in the SCB.

nominal voltage level corresponding to 110, 220 or 380 V is set directly on the inputs of the relay cabinets of the automatic blocking devices and the busbars of the input panels of the EC posts. Deviations from the specified values are allowed in the direction of a decrease of no more than 10% and in the direction of an increase of no more than 5%. Almost all SCB users use a phase voltage of 220 V. However, the minimum voltage level of 198 V turns out to be at the extremely low voltage of the generation failure of the frequency converters.

The settings of the voltage control relay on the input panels of the SCB devices are accepted within 204...208 V at a nominal voltage of 220 V and 340...345 V at a nominal voltage of 380 V.

In the considered conditions, the installation of an autonomous inverter, which is turned on in series and receives power from both the network and the battery (Fig. 3.4), allows you to significantly increase the reliability of the system of linear consumers.

Fig. 3.4. Connection diagram of the working power supply line to the inverter with a battery
(BAT – battery, INV – inverter, OT – own-needs power transformers) (Source: Own study)

The introduction of the specified system with the use of network inverters and modern storage batteries will significantly improve the situation with the reliability of providing electrical energy to linear consumers.

A feature of modern railway transport systems is the rapid development of information systems, which in recent years have also become control systems and provide the necessary level of traffic safety and their main operational characteristics. The nature of work, requirements for electrical energy supply systems, level of consumption, etc. are important. Having performed an analysis of modern electrical energy supply systems based on renewable energy sources and its accumulation, it is possible to develop new principles and principles for the construction of such systems

3.3 Development of power supply systems on railways.

The power supply of station equipment and communication on railway transport is provided by direct current sources with a certain range of nominal voltage (24, 48, 60, 110 220 V, etc.). The main power supply systems include: autonomous, buffer, batteryless, and combined (Fig. 3.5) [190].

Fig. 3.5 Structural diagram of the power supply system (Source: own study based on [190])

The autonomous system is intended for powering portable and stationary automation and communication equipment, and all others are for powering stationary equipment. When considering the features of the operation of the *autonomous power supply system*, special attention needs to be paid to the operation of the system in the "charge-discharge" mode, which is effective in conditions of frequent changes in the parameters of the network's electrical energy source. The essence of this method is that a separate $UZ1-UZn$ rectifier and two or more $GB1-GBn$ batteries are used for each voltage gradation (Fig. 3.6).

Fig. 3.6 Scheme of providing electrical energy by the "charge-discharge" method (DSB – direct current bus; 1,2,3 – battery groups) (Source: own study based on [190])

One battery supplies power to the electrical energy receiver, while the other is charged and remains in reserve. As soon as the battery is discharged to a certain state, it is disconnected and connected to the rectifier, while a backup battery is used to power the equipment. When using this method, the battery is charged in constant current mode. The capacity for such batteries is determined based on a fairly significant duration of their use (at the level of 12-24 hours), so such systems are often quite bulky and require a separate room. A feature of this method is also mandatory observation of the charge-discharge mode, which may cause additional operational costs. the next limitation regarding the use of such systems is a rather low efficiency at the level of 30-40%.

Buffer power supply system.

When organizing the operation of such a system, a battery is connected in parallel to the UZ rectifier and the load (Fig. 3.7). In the event of an emergency mode in the network or damage to the rectifier, further power supply to the load is provided continuously.

Fig. 3.6 Scheme of the buffer power supply system (Source: own study based on [190])

When using such a power supply system, three modes of operation are possible: medium current, pulse and continuous recharging (Fig. 3.8a-b).

In the medium current mode (Fig. 3.8a), the rectifier is connected in parallel with the battery and ensures the flow of constant charging current regardless of load changes. It is characterized by a fairly significant change in battery voltage and allows the use of the simplest rectifiers without automatic adjustment. The current of the rectifier is calculated based on the amount of electrical energy needed to support the load during the day. The disadvantages of the mode include the impossibility of accurately determining the current of the rectifier (due to the unknown nature of the load change), which leads to undercharging or overcharging of batteries; relatively short service life of batteries (due to deep charge and discharge cycles); significant changes in voltage, which is dangerous for sensitive equipment.

In pulse recharging mode (Fig. 3.8b), the rectifier current changes in leaps and bounds depending on the battery voltage. It affects the mode of operation of the rectifier, either it provides power to the load together with the battery, or it feeds the load and recharges the battery. The advantage of this method is a fairly simple regulation system; small limits of voltage change on the battery and load; longer battery life compared to the previous method.

a) b)

Fig. 3.8 Scheme of the buffer power supply system in different modes: a – medium current and continuous recharging; b - pulse recharging
(Source: own study based on [190])

The circuit implementation of the continuous recharging mode is similar to the circuit in [fig. 3.8a](#). The difference is that a charged storage battery receives a small direct charging current from the rectifier, which compensates for its self-discharge. To ensure such a mode, it is necessary to have a rectifier with the ability to adjust the value of the output voltage, while the adjustment error should not exceed 2%. Failure to comply with this requirement leads to rapid failure of the batteries. The advantage of this method is a sufficiently high efficiency; long service life; high voltage stability at the output of the rectifier; reduction of operating costs due to the automation of the service process. The disadvantage is the complication of power supply devices due to the use of stabilization and automation elements.

Battery-free and combined power systems

Battery-free systems do not have a battery and the required level of reliability is provided by schematic or design solutions. An example of such a system is the use of a diesel generator ([Fig. 3.9](#)) and a reserve network feeder. In the event of an accident, another independent source of alternating current energy is connected through the backup feeder, if the accident occurred on both connections, is automatically started **DGA**. The disadvantage of the system is the presence of interruptions in the power supply both when switching to the backup feeder (up to 1.3 s) and when switching to the nominal mode of the **DGA** (25...30 s).

The use of the beam scheme ([Fig. 3.10](#)) allows you to connect the equipment to two feeders that are independent of each other.

Fig. 3.9 Diagram of a power supply system with a **DGA** and a backup feeder
(Source: own study based on [190])

Fig. 3.10 Two-beam scheme power systems
(Source: own study based on [190])

At the same time, the external energy source and the rectifier form an independent circuit, which is called a beam. In the event of an accident of one beam, its load is connected to the remaining source, and at the same time, the **DGA** is started

in automatic mode. After the output of the DGA to the nominal mode of operation, part of the equipment is connected to it and the scheme is restored. A general disadvantage of battery-free systems is the presence of DHA with increased operating costs, the need to have a certain fuel supply, etc.

A feature of the combined system is the use of a battery operating in buffer mode for the most responsible equipment link, all others are battery-free (Fig. 3.11a). In the power system with DC converters, several converters with different nominal voltages are used for power supply, which are connected to the battery in the event of an accident. Another option for providing equipment with electrical energy in the event of an accident is the use of inverters (Fig. 3.11b).

Fig. 3.11 Power scheme with DC converters (a) and inverters (b)
(Source: own study based on [190])

The considered schemes for providing electrical energy for communication equipment and automation were developed based on certain conditions, namely the availability and characteristics of the energy source (mains, DGA, battery of a certain type). Taking into account the current trends in the development of pulsed power supply systems, an important indicator is the provision of electromagnetic compatibility due to their sensitivity to unauthorized voltage disconnection, which also requires solving a number of problems. According to the analysis of failures of complex computing equipment (Fig. 3.12), the largest number is the failure of power supply devices - at the level of 45.3%, which affects the quality of the functioning of the entire transportation process.

The main direction of increasing the reliability of the power supply of information systems is the redundancy of power feeders. According to the current regulatory documents, two independent power sources from the network with the possibility of using a third from the DGA are necessary to provide electricity to consumers of the 1st category of electricity supply.

Fig. 3.12 Distribution of types of computer equipment failures:

1 – failure of power supply devices (45%); 2 – thunderstorms (9.4%); 3 – fires and explosions (8.2%); 4 – hardware and software failures (8.2%); 5 – floods (6.7%); 6 – earthquakes (5.5%); 7 – problems with electrical connections (4.5%); 8 – personnel errors (3.2%); 9 – failure of control systems (2.3%); 10 – others (6.7%)
(Source: own study based on [190])

The increased requirements for the provision of electrical energy for information systems and the current [regulatory documents](#) can be compared using table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Requirements for the quality of electrical energy of information systems (Source: own study based on [190])

№ p/p	Indicators	EE quality standards according to GOST 13109-97	EE quality standards for information systems
1	Voltage deviation	+5 %	+1%
2	Frequency deviation	+0.1 Hz	+0.1 Hz
3	Voltage fluctuations	+10 %	+1 %
4	Voltage failure	lasting up to 30 s	Inadmissible
5	Temporary overvoltage	k-t 1.47	Inadmissible
6	Voltage pulse	up to 4.5 kV lasting up to 10 ms	Inadmissible

Based on the specifics of information systems, the most important indicator is ensuring the stability of the constant voltage that powers these systems. This requirement has an impact on the use of traditional power sources used in the relay

equipment of SCB devices, for which the change in voltage is permissible at the level of $\pm 10\%$. Another feature of **computing devices** is their relatively low immunity to interference, which is due to the high speed of **computing devices** and digital principles of information processing. For SCB relay equipment, impulse disturbances with a duration from a fraction of a microsecond to tens of milliseconds and an amplitude of up to several tens, and sometimes even hundreds of volts, practically do not affect the reliability of operation, which cannot be said about the means of logic ICs. The overloading capacity of the IMS according to the value of the supply voltage due to their insignificant power does not allow an increase in the voltage at the level of 5-10% of the nominal value.

According to the time values shown in **Fig. 3.13**, the duration of the switching process is approximately 0.4 s, although in some cases, due to the presence of oil switches, a low degree of automation, etc., the switching time interval can increase to 1.3 s. Computer equipment, on which information systems are built, are characterized by increased requirements for ensuring the reliability of power supply, since even short-term shutdowns from the source of electrical energy can lead to a complete or partial loss of information in their memory devices.

Fig. 3.13 Voltage oscillogram when switching from the main feeder to the backup (Source: Own study)

The given characteristic does not meet the requirements for systems of this type and requires an analysis of existing technical solutions in the system of uninterrupted supply of electrical energy to various equipment.

3.4 Uninterruptible power supply systems

You can increase the reliability of the specified systems by using an Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS). These devices are connected between primary alternating voltage networks and power sources of computing equipment. They are characterized by the following modes of operation: main – UPS operation is provided by the primary energy source and autonomous, when the UPS is disconnected from the network and switched to battery operation. The transition from one mode to another occurs due to the appropriate control and management schemes, which ensure constant monitoring of parameters and perform appropriate switching.

The input voltage of the UPS is the AC voltage current 220 or 380 V, with a frequency of 50 Hz. There are studies of the level of power supply voltages in the domestic power supply system on the railway [186], which indicate fairly wide limits from 160...260 V. What is more, these data correspond to static, i.e. "slow" changes in voltage, while impulse deviations can reach much larger values. Modes of power supply voltage disappearance for a few seconds are also possible, and in emergency mode – much longer. Due to the presence of such powerful interference generators (traction substations, catenary network, means of electric traction, etc.) on railway transport facilities, short-term impulse and high-frequency disturbances of significant amplitude often occur, which significantly affect the operation of these systems. The nominal power varies widely from 100-200 W to tens of kW. Depending on the type of batteries used in the UPS, they can provide autonomous operation from several minutes to several hours. the most common type of batteries are lead-acid, sealed, maintenance-free. In systems of significant power, DGA is used to reduce the capacity and, accordingly, the cost of storage batteries. Designed for operation in the temperature range from 0 to 40°C and relative humidity of 90%.

The principle of construction and operation of UPS

In accordance with the international standard IEC 60146-4, UPS are divided into four main groups: with the network turned off ("off-line"), line-interactive type ("line-interactive"), with the network turned on ("on-line") and modular. The functional scheme of the "off-line" UPS is shown in Fig. 3.14.

Fig. 3.14 Functional diagram of an "off-line" UPS (Source: own study based on [190])

In the main mode of operation, when the alternating voltage meets the relevant quality indicators, the load is fed through the filter, and the batteries are charged through the rectifier at the same time. If the quality indicators fall below the set limit, it is switched to autonomous mode and the load is fed through the inverter. The specified system allows you to supply the load with electrical energy quite quickly: when the inverter is connected, the contact switching time is 4-15 ms, and when it is turned off, it takes 200 ms.

The disadvantage of such a system is unsatisfactory operation in conditions of low quality power supply voltage. In this case, constant switching of the S contact will be observed and the batteries will not be charged to the required level. That is, the "off-line" mode means that in case of unacceptable voltage deviations, the load is disconnected from the network and connected to the inverter. The functional diagram of the "line-interactive" type UPS is shown (Fig. 3.15)

Fig. 3.15 Functional diagram of a line-interactive UPS (Source: own study based on [190])

Its difference from the circuit in Fig. 3.14 is the presence of a regulator that improves the quality of the supply voltage in the operating mode. The regulator is made in the form of a step voltage switch, based on a transformer or an autotransformer. In some cases, it is possible to use variable voltage stabilizers. The main advantage of the given scheme is a much smaller number of switching to offline mode. This feature allows you to reduce the capacity of the batteries and reduce the requirements for the filtration system, which reduces the total cost of the system. Although with long interruptions in the power supply, the noted shortcomings remain

Better reliability and voltage quality indicators are provided by the circuit shown in Fig. 3.16.

Fig. 3.16 Functional diagram of an "on-line" UPS (Source: own study based on [190])

The difference of the given scheme is the presence of a constant voltage converter (DCV), which allows to ensure the continuity of the inverter and the exclusion of transient processes during its switching. The above scheme is characterized by high stability of the supply voltage, and the presence of an IPN pulse converter allows to provide better protection against overloads. The disadvantage of the given scheme is lower efficiency compared to other schemes, which is due to the double power conversion of constant voltage and the higher cost associated with the presence of two EE converters.

A further development of the "on-line" scheme is the use of an additional passive channel (by-pass), which is designed to transfer energy from the source to the load in normal mode. The functional scheme of the UPS will have the form shown in Fig. 3.17. The latest models of the UPS provide switching it to the "by-pass" mode, without transient processes in the load (intelligent by-pass).

Fig. 3.17 Functional diagram of an "on-line by-pass" type UPS (Source: own study based on [190])

In accordance with the current regulatory documents, the limit of possible changes in the average value of the primary voltage is 183...260 V for post devices, for floor devices - 60...260 V, provided the nominal voltage is 220 V.

The power value is calculated from the expression

$$P_{EX UPS} = k_{mar} \frac{\sum P_{t(max)}}{\cos \varphi},$$

where k_{mar} – margin factor determined by impulse processes in computing equipment (usually equal to 1.3); $\sum P_{t(max)}$ – total maximum power consumed by the load; $\cos \varphi$ – the load power factor of the secondary power source (varies widely from 0.6 to 0.98).

The time during which the load will be supplied with electrical energy from the UPS in autonomous operation mode is determined based on the conditions for eliminating the consequences of the accident by maintenance or repair personnel (5-15 min - for household load, 30 min or more - for complex computing complexes, etc.). Based on the above overview of uninterruptible power supply systems, the best

characteristics are achieved in the "on-line" UPS scheme. The construction of such systems occurs in two ways: according to the centralized and decentralized principle. The centralized principle allows you to build a single system of energy transformation, stabilization and distribution with one or several DGA, in turn, decentralized - requires the installation of a large number of low-power UPS.

A modern power supply unit (Fig. 3.18) is a set of equipment from input and distribution devices and uninterruptible power supply systems, whose purpose is to provide a continuous power supply of railway automation and remote control systems and devices with the necessary for their reliable functioning quality of electricity. Diagnostic objects that could be identified are listed below.

Fig. 3.18 Power supply unit structure (Source: [191])

For directly external power sources (power supply feeders) voltage, currents and the quality of the supplied electric power must be monitored. On interlockings belonging to a special group of the first category, where a reserve autonomous power plant (RAPP) is used as the third energy source, it is necessary to monitor its condition by the following parameters: voltage, current, and frequency of the current at the output of the RAPP, fuel level in the tank, oil level in the engine, coolant temperature. In the input devices it is necessary to monitor the state of the device for protection against impulse overvoltages and switching devices. In switchgears, it is necessary to monitor the status of contactors implementing automatic reserve input, voltage monitoring relay and protective devices. In UPS, the main object of diagnosis is the

battery. The following parameters must be: voltage, charge current and discharge current, temperature, capacity. It is important to measure the temperature both inside the cabinet and outside – in the room of the power supply unit. It is also necessary to monitor the operability of the converters (rectifiers, inverters, converters) and cooling fans in the UPS. In addition, an important object of diagnosis is insulation resistance of cables, installation and galvanically isolated from the ground devices.

Fig. 3.19 shows the structural diagram of the electrical energy supply of the dispatch control system. In this scheme, electrical energy with an operating voltage of 380/220 V, which is connected to an external network and a backup diesel generator, enters the input of a large-capacity UPS.

Fig. 3.19 Structural diagram of information systems power supply
(Source: own study based on [190])

An external bypass is provided for regular preventive maintenance in the UPS or battery. System reliability is increased by UPS redundancy. Station devices of automation of main railway transport mainly receive electricity from three-phase transformer substations with a secondary voltage of 380/220 V with a solidly grounded neutral. According to the given table, the basic diagram of the power supply of information systems will have the form shown in Fig. 3.20.

In the main mode, the system receives power from 1 or 2 feeders with an operating voltage of 3*220 V, galvanic isolation is provided by means of an isolation

transformer TV1 with an isolated neutral. After the transformer, through the input filter, the electricity enters the UPS, where it is converted from alternating current to direct current on the control rectifier, filtering of high-frequency components on the filter, charging the battery and reverse conversion using an inverter. The converted electrical energy is again filtered using the output filter and fed to the load through the separation transformer TV2.

Fig. 3.20 Schematic diagram of power supply of information systems
(Source: own study based on [190])

In the mode of switching power feeders, the supply of electrical energy does not disappear due to the operation of the inverter from the battery. In the emergency mode, which is characterized by a long-term absence of external voltage from the power system. The load in the system receives electrical energy from the DGA or from the batteries, if the starts the DGA is not possible. In the event of a UPS failure, the load is bypassed by a manual or automatic bypass.

The DGA automatically turns on the load approximately 60 seconds after the voltage on both feeders disappears and turns it off after the voltage is restored on one of the feeders. Control of the voltage level on both feeders is carried out by a special relay. With the same voltage level on feeders 1 and 2, the circuit solution (installation of jumpers) ensures the predominance of feeder 1 (main power). When the voltage on at least one of the phases of feeder 1 drops below the return level of the voltage control relay, there will be an instant switchover of power to the backup feeder 2 and an instant reverse return to feeder 1 when the voltage on it is restored, exceeding the setting for the operation of its control relays.

By setting the corresponding jumpers, it is possible to ensure the advantage of feeder 2 or to set the switching of feeders without an advantage. The time of transition from feeder to feeder is from 0.05 to 0.3 s. The system with the advantage of feeder 1 and with instant return often creates failures in the control system and overlaps of signals during switching of high-voltage feeders in the cycle of [AIR - ARI](#).

It is possible to increase the reliability of the considered system due to automatic uninterruptible UPS. Such devices are equipped with rechargeable batteries and an inverter, and in the event of an accident, they allow you to switch to working mode almost instantly due to the use of transistor switches.

3.5 Prospects for the development of autonomous systems of uninterrupted power supply of linear consumers

Consumer parameters by capacity and level of consumption are given in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. Photoelectric systems, due to their simple structure and ease of automation, as well as free and easily accessible primary energy, allow us to recommend them as the main ones in the autonomous power supply system. In order to maximize the use of solar energy, devices that track the movement of the sun in the sky, so-called "Santractors", are used. Determining the azimuth and altitude of the sun is possible at any time and for any geographic coordinates using the following formulas [185]:

$$H = \arcsin[\cos(L)\cos(\delta)\cos(h_s) + \sin(L)\sin(\delta)] \quad (3.1)$$

$$A = \arcsin\left[\frac{\cos(\delta)\sin(h_s)}{\cos(H)}\right]$$

where $\cos(h_s) > \tan(\delta)/\tan(L)$

where $\cos(h_s) < \tan(\delta)/\tan(L)$ $A = -\arcsin\left[\frac{\cos(\delta)\sin(h_s)}{\cos(H)}\right]$

H is the angle of incidence of the sun; A – azimuth; L is the geographical latitude of the installation site; h_s – hourly solar angle; δ is the inclination of the sun.

Solar panels should be oriented to the south. The angle of inclination to the horizontal plane should be approximately $50\text{-}55^\circ$ in winter and $34\text{-}37^\circ$ in summer. In some implementation options, solar cells can be placed on special bases that place them perpendicular to the sun's rays.

The installed capacity of solar cells, incorrectly marked in the catalogs with Wp (peak watt), is given for an insolation of 1000 W/m^2 and a semiconductor junction temperature of 20°C . Such conditions occur quite sporadically. For this reason, the installed capacity of the solar cell is only used for about 1,000 hours per year. By applying the sun tracking formulas above, this time can be increased to about 1200 hours per year. On average, in Poland, you can get about 100 W from one square meter of battery area.

When evaluating the generation capacity of a photovoltaic installation (PEU), it is necessary to remember that the intensity of solar radiation I_T , kW/m^2 on an inclined surface, in the general case is determined by the expression

$$I_T = I_B R_B + I_D R_D + \rho (I_B + I_D) \frac{1 - \cos \beta}{2} \quad (3.2).$$

Here, the first term describes direct radiation, the second - scattered, and the last - reflected. Magnitudes I_B and I_D in the given expression - the intensity of direct and scattered radiation on the horizontal plane, which are determined from the reference data; ρ – albedo of the Earth; R_B and R_D – coefficients necessary for calculating direct and scattered components for an inclined plane; $R_B = \frac{\cos \theta}{\cos \varphi}$ – for direct radiation, where φ – the angle of the Sun at the zenith, θ – angle of incidence; R_D – for scattered radiation, using existing models.

In the case of using PV modules for autonomous operation, when performing calculations, it is necessary to take into account, first of all, the stable mode of providing consumers with electrical energy, and not the maximum electrical energy, which is more typical for network PV modules.

An example of the influence of the angle of inclination of the photovoltaic panel on the level of electrical energy production is shown in Figure 3.21. The graph shows the power that reaches the earth's surface and the possible options for placing the modules at different angles from 0 to 50° throughout the year. When performing the analysis, the geographical data of Warsaw (latitude 37°) were used, the data of the solar radiation components were obtained from. From the obtained dependences, it

can be concluded that the most favorable mode of operation of the autonomous PV plant will be observed at an angle of inclination of 50° , at other angles, although the total annual energy production is more, there is a deficit of generation in the most favorable months.

Fig. 3.21 Dependence of the intensity of solar radiation during the year when the angle changes from 0 to 50° (Source: Own study)

When evaluating the power of the system in the most unfavorable period, the capacity of the batteries is overestimated. Given the fact that energy storage is the most expensive component today, this leads to an unjustified overestimation of the total cost of the entire system.

The source of guaranteed power in the system will be a lithium-ion battery, which allows to ensure a longer service life, allows to automate the process of diagnostics and charge management [see section 2]. Such a system is generally called a solar photovoltaic installation (Fig. 3.22).

The following elements can be distinguished in its structure: photovoltaic modules (PV-generator) with supporting fittings, communication cables, and, depending on the type of system, an electronic inverter and a charge controller with a storage battery. In sunny weather, the source of electricity is a solar battery that charges the battery, when it is fully charged, the solar generator stops working. Due

to the use of the inverter, the possibility of supplying electricity to the consumer is ensured.

Fig. 3.22 Functional scheme of the power supply system of individual consumers
(Source: Own study)

The charge controller controls and manages the entire system, primarily in order to guarantee maximum efficiency in the use of generated energy. Some manufacturers include in the set of functions of the regulator a controlled recharging to equalize the voltage on the battery accumulators. To obtain the required power and operating voltage, the modules are connected in series or in parallel, the more carefully selected modules in the battery (or the smaller the difference in the characteristics of the modules), the less loss of electrical energy.

Photoelectric modules must be equipped with special protection against excessive discharge, which is provided by disconnecting the load. This protection is triggered when the battery voltage drops below the cut-off voltage. The load cannot be connected until the voltage rises to a certain threshold (connection voltage). Taking into account the given circumstance, when designing systems for providing linear consumers, it is necessary to determine the optimal capacity of the AB system, taking into account the solar generation capabilities of the corresponding region (BESS).

CONCLUSION

The study considers some aspects related to the development of RES in railway power supply systems. The extent of their application in the traction line, non-traction power supply system, for power supply of traffic control equipment, etc. was described. Particular attention was paid to the analysis of electrical energy storage systems using regeneration of energy, accumulation systems, superfluous and super capacitors. It was discussed the experience of RES application on the example of the structure of Ukrainian and European railways.

As a result of the performed scientific research, the following scientific and practical results were obtained:

1. The analysis of the possibility of building a local power system on the basis of the graphs of the traction substation load, taking into account the type and capacity of RES means (namely wind and solar energy), taking into account their real energy characteristics in the relevant climatic conditions, allows to assess the degree of their influence on the level of stability of power supply.

2. A mathematical model for assessing electricity needs and load behavior (i.e. consumption level) in time allows to assess of the real possibilities of using RES taking into account the need for ensuring the proper quality of power supply.

3. It's analyzed the structure of the power supply system of railway traffic control devices that require high reliability of power supply. It has been established that solar systems equipped with energy storage devices are the most acceptable for this type of devices. Obtained dependencies that allow to determine the optimal characteristics of the panels, of autonomous PV stations, taking into account the capacity of the energy storage system and the level of electricity consumption of the railway traffic control system.

4. Analysis of existing electric energy storage systems is carried out. The field of application of certain types of AB for the conditions of traction networks is established, taking into account the nature and capacity of the load, as well as the conditions of their use.

5. The effective use of RES in railway power supply systems is possible based on complex application of several sources of different nature (solar and wind generation), and it is important to determine the share of each energy source. It has been established that the efficiency of energy storage has a significant dependence on the capacity of the battery, instead, the performance is less important at those rates of power change that are inherent in wind energy or its combination with solar energy. The peculiarity of combined power systems with RES is the multiplicity of battery

charging/discharging cycles. The need for accumulation to ensure a reliable energy balance significantly (at times) depends on the ability to predict the generation of RES, which forms a planned schedule of load on the power system.

The obtained results made it possible to formulate requirements for autonomous systems for providing electricity in the conditions of providing the necessary level of reliability of power supply of a special group (equipment of electrical signaling and automation) and determine the prospects for their application. One of the result of the work is the development of the recommendations for the autonomous power supply system of anti-theft system of overhead contact line. The anti-theft system was developed in the framework of the project No.: POIR 04.01.01.00-0018/17 co-financed by the National Centre for Research and Development entitled: "Development and implementation of elements of the anti-theft system of the overhead contact line in rail transport".

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